

JOURNAL of ENDODONTICS and RESTORATIVE DENTISTRY

SHAPING THE FUTURE OF ENDODONTICS AND RESTORATIVE CARE

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4

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4

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1

2026

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Aims & Scope

Journal of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry (J Endod Restor Dent) is a highly respected scientific journal that caters to the needs of those interested in the fields of endodontics and restorative dentistry. This online-only journal follows a rigorous and independent peer-review process, ensuring that all articles are unbiased and of the highest quality. The double-blinded approach employed by Journal of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry further strengthens its credibility, making it a trusted source of information for researchers, practitioners, and students alike. With its biannual release schedule, readers can look forward to two new issues each year, in March and September. Overall, Journal of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry is a valuable resource for anyone seeking to stay up-to-date on the latest developments in these important areas of dental science.

Journal of Endodontics and Restorative Dentistry provides extensive coverage of both clinical and experimental studies on all aspects of endodontics and restorative dentistry. Notably, the journal features original articles, reviews on current topics, case reports, editorial comments, and letters to the editor that follow ethical guidelines. It is important to note that the journal is published solely in English, ensuring it maintains a global reach and fosters international collaboration within the field.

The journal's editorial and publication processes are meticulously designed to meet the highest standards of integrity and quality. To ensure this, the journal adheres to the guidelines set by several reputable organizations such as the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE), World Association of Medical Editors (WAME), Council of Science Editors (CSE), Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE), European Association of Science Editors (EASE), and National Information Standards Organization (NISO). Furthermore, the journal is committed to upholding the Principles of Transparency and Best Practice in Scholarly Publishing, which have been laid out by the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) at doaj.org/bestpractice.

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Original Article

Global Trends in Micro-CT Studies of Root Canal Morphology: A 25-Year Bibliometric Analysis

Özge Başar^a

^a Turkuaz Dental Clinic, İzmir, Türkiye

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01.10.2025
Completion of First Review: 23.10.2025
Accepted: 02.11.2025
Published: 01.03.2026

KEYWORDS

Endodontics
Micro-computed tomography
Root Canal Morphology
Scientometric analysis

CORRESPONDENCE

Özge Başar
Turkuaz Dental Clinic, İzmir, Türkiye
E-mail: goren.ozge@hotmail.com

CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

Micro-CT offers precise, non-destructive visualization of canal morphology, providing valuable insights into complex internal anatomy. These insights have improved the understanding of canal configurations, refined experimental models, and guided the advancement of clinical techniques and instrumentation strategies endodontic practice.

ABSTRACT

Objectives: This study aimed to conduct a bibliometric analysis of publications on the use of micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) in root canal morphology research to map scientific output, assess collaboration patterns, and identify thematic trends.

Materials and Methods: Articles published between 2000 and 2025 were retrieved from the Web of Science Core Collection (WoSCC), limited to the Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-Expanded). After applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, eligible studies were analyzed by publication year, authorship, country of origin, journal and keyword occurrence. Data were processed using Microsoft Excel, and bibliometric networks were visualized in VOSviewer (v1.6.15).

Results: Publication output increased steadily after 2010, reaching a plateau during 2020. Brazil, the United States, and China were the most productive countries, together contributing over 60% of all SCI-indexed articles, while Türkiye, Germany, and Switzerland also showed notable growth. Versiani, Sousa-Neto, and Keleş were among the most prolific and influential authors. Keyword mapping revealed three main clusters: instrumentation and preparation, imaging-based anatomical analysis, and cone-beam computed tomography.

Conclusion: Micro-CT has become an essential imaging tool in endodontic morphology research, allowing precise three-dimensional evaluation of root canal anatomy. Although it was initially used mainly for validation purposes, it has progressively evolved into a comprehensive tool for detailed assessment of root canal morphology and quantitative analysis in endodontic studies.

1. Introduction

Understanding the complex three-dimensional morphology of the root canal system remains one of the most critical factors influencing the success of endodontic therapy. Incomplete knowledge of internal anatomy can result in missed canals, inadequate cleaning, and persistent infection, all of which may lead to endodontic failure.¹ Traditional imaging modalities have provided valuable information about canal anatomy; however, their two-dimensional limitations often prevent an accurate appreciation of internal morphology, canal curvature, and anatomical variations. These constraints have driven the continuous development and adoption of advanced imaging technologies in endodontic research.²

Micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) has emerged as the widely accepted reference method for non-destructive, high-resolution three-dimensional imaging of dental hard tissues. This technique allows precise visualization and quantitative evaluation of root canal morphology, including canal number, shape, curvature, volume, surface area, and accessory structures.³ Compared with histological sectioning and radiographic methods, micro-CT provides superior spatial resolution and reproducibility while preserving the specimen integrity. Consequently, micro-CT has become an indispensable tool in studies of internal root anatomy, instrumentation efficacy, sealer penetration, obturation quality, and morphological variations among different populations and tooth types.⁴

Since its first applications in dental research during the early 2000s, micro-CT has progressively transformed endodontic research methodologies.⁴ Early studies focused primarily on validating its accuracy and reliability relative to conventional

techniques.⁵⁻⁷ Subsequently, as scanner availability increased and analytical software advanced, researchers began to explore the technology's potential to quantify complex anatomical details and to compare pre- and post-instrumentation morphology.^{8,9} These methodological advances have contributed to significant progress in understanding canal configurations, apical anatomy, isthmus prevalence, and the effects of age, ethnicity, and clinical interventions on root canal systems.¹⁰⁻¹² Furthermore, the incorporation of micro-CT-based datasets into digital modeling and artificial intelligence pipelines has expanded its relevance beyond pure morphology studies, positioning it as a central research instrument in endodontic innovation.^{13,14}

Although several overviews^{4,15,16} have addressed the general applications of micro-CT in dentistry, no comprehensive bibliometric analysis has specifically focused on its use in root canal morphology — one of the most extensively investigated areas within endodontic research. Bibliometric analysis provides a quantitative approach to filling this gap by mapping scientific output, evaluating authorship and collaboration networks, and identifying thematic evolution across time. Such analyses not only highlight the trajectory of technological integration but also reveal geographic and institutional trends that shape the global distribution of endodontic research activity.¹⁷ Analyzing publication output, citation impact, author and country collaborations, and keyword co-occurrence can reveal both established and emerging themes that define this research domain.¹⁸ Furthermore, identifying the most active contributors, core journals, and leading countries provides valuable insight into the academic landscape supporting innovation in endodontic

imaging.¹⁹ This study differs from previous bibliometric assessments by focusing exclusively on micro-CT applications in root canal morphology, rather than general dental or imaging contexts. Earlier studies often presented different dental applications of micro-CT,¹⁵ limiting the ability to identify morphology-specific trends, author networks, and technological evolution. By refining the dataset to include only SCI-indexed studies explicitly addressing root canal anatomy, the present work provides a targeted and methodologically standardized overview of how micro-CT has shaped endodontic morphology research over the past 25 years.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Design

This bibliometric analysis was conducted in accordance with established guidelines for reporting bibliometric studies in biomedical research.²⁰

2.2. Search Strategy

A cross-sectional bibliometric analysis was conducted to assess global publication trends on the use of micro-CT in research on root canal morphology between 2000 and 2025. The literature search was carried out on September 20, 2025, using the Web of Science Core Collection (WoSCC) database, which includes the Science Citation Index Expanded (SCI-Expanded). The search strategy employed the keywords "micro-CT" OR "micro-computed tomography", "morphology" OR "anatomy", and "endodontic" OR "root canal" in the "All Fields" category. The exact search string was as follows: (micro-CT OR micro-computed tomography) AND (morphology OR anatomy) AND (endodontic OR root canal). The initial search yielded 506 records. After excluding conference proceedings, letters, editorials, and notes, and limiting the results to original research articles and review papers published in English, the dataset was refined by applying the publication year filter (2000–2025). After detailed evaluation, studies unrelated to the use of micro-CT in endodontic morphology research were excluded. The "full records and cited references" of each included article were exported from WoSCC in plain-text format to ensure compatibility with bibliometric analysis software.

2.4. Data analysis

Data obtained from the WoSCC database were organized and analyzed in Microsoft Excel 2021 (Microsoft, USA) to perform preliminary data management, descriptive evaluation, and trend analysis. Network visualization was performed using the VOSviewer software (version 1.6.15; Centre for Science and Technology Studies, Leiden University, Netherlands). The overall workflow of the study was presented in Fig. 1.

Publication output and citation counts were calculated. Country-level publication data were extracted from the WoSCC dataset. The co-authorship analysis was performed in VOSviewer (v.1.6.15) using the full counting method. A minimum threshold of 2 documents per author was applied. The resulting data were organized to identify the most prolific contributors. Country-level analyses were conducted under the same condition. Additionally, a thesaurus file was used to merge the country name variants "Turkey" and "Türkiye" under the standardized label "Türkiye" to ensure consistency in the co-authorship and collaboration networks. The distribution of publications across journals was analyzed, and the top 10 journals were identified based on record counts. A keyword co-occurrence network was constructed to reveal thematic clusters. The minimum occurrence threshold for inclusion was set at 3 for author keywords to include only terms with consistent relevance. A thesaurus file was created in

Fig. 1. Flowchart of the Literature Search and Selection Process

VOSviewer to standardize terminology, merging all variations of "microcomputed tomography," "micro computed tomography," "micro-computed tomography (scan/scanning)," "microct," "micro ct," "micro-ct," and "microtomography" under a single unified term, "micro-CT", allowing for clearer clustering and a more accurate and visually streamlined map of the keyword network.

In all network maps, the node size represented the frequency of occurrence or publication volume, with larger nodes indicating higher relevance or output. The thickness of connecting lines reflected the strength of the relationships between items, and the color of each node denoted the cluster to which it belonged. All analyses were performed to provide a comprehensive overview of publication trends, influential authors, and thematic developments in the application of micro-CT for root canal morphology research.

3. Results

The refined dataset comprised 499 English-language records; 482 (96.6%) were classified under Dentistry/Oral Medicine and 409 (82.0%) were SCI-indexed. Annual output increased across the study period, with a clear inflection after 2010 and sustained activity through the 2020s. Production followed three phases: 2000–2009, low but steady growth as micro-CT platforms entered dental morphology; 2010–2016, acceleration with wider scanner availability and established workflows; 2017–2025, consolidation at higher volumes with multi-country collaboration networks and recurring morphology themes. The trend line shows no late-period collapse, indicating durable adoption rather than a transient peak (Fig. 2).

The top three countries—Brazil (91; 22.25%), the USA (86; 21.03%), and China (79; 19.32%) accounted for 62.6% of all records. They were followed by Türkiye, Germany, and Switzerland (Table 1).

Publication leadership was held by Versiani, Marco Aurélio (n=32), followed by Sousa-Neto, Manoel Damião (n=21) and Keleş, Ali (n=17). Duarte, Marco AH, Wolf, Thomas Gerhard, and

Fig. 2. Yearly output and citation counts (WoSCC, 2000–2025).

Table 1. Top 10 Authors by Publications

Rank	Author	Publications
1	Versiani, Marco Aurélio	32
2	Sousa-Neto, Manoel Damiao	21
3	Keleş, Ali	17
4	Duarte, Marco AH	16
5	Wolf, Thomas Gerhard	16
6	Gutmann, James	16
7	Paqué, Frank	15
8	Ordinola-Zapata, Ronald	15
9	Keskin, Cangul	14
10	Ahmed, Hany Mohamed Aly	14

Gutmann, James each have 16 publications. Paqué and Ronald have 15, while Keskin and Ahmed have 14 each. The 11-publication gap between the first and second positions indicates a right-skewed distribution with a concentrated top tier and tight clustering in the lower ranks (Table 2).

The co-authorship network comprises 11 distinct clusters (Fig. 3). The largest is Brazil-centered, anchored by Sousa-Neto, Versiani, Ordinola-Zapata, Duarte, and Tanomaru-Filho. A Korean-centered cluster (Lee Jong-Ki, Lee Woo-Cheol, and Oh, Kum) shows strong internal ties but limited external links. Authors like Keleş and Belladonna function as critical bridges, linking multiple diverse clusters across the map. While Ahmed and colleagues form a noticeable sub-cluster, Gu, Y. appears as a small, isolated satellite group, highlighting the specialized and diverse nature of collaboration within this global research field.

The cross-country collaboration network (Fig. 4) revealed strong international partnerships centered around Brazil, China, and the USA, which represented the largest and most interconnected nodes. Germany, Switzerland, Italy, and Türkiye also emerged as key contributors with extensive cooperative links. The dense interconnections among these core countries indicate a highly globalized research landscape, characterized by active knowledge exchange and co-authorship across Europe, Asia, North America, and South America.

As shown in Table 3, the Journal of Endodontics and International Endodontic Journal accounted for the majority of publications (27.1% and 13.9%, respectively), followed by Clinical Oral Investigations and BMC Oral Health.

The keyword co-occurrence analysis (Fig. 5) revealed that ‘micro-CT’ was strongly linked to ‘root canal preparation,’ ‘anatomy,’ and ‘cone-beam computed tomography.’ After thesaurus merging and a minimum occurrence threshold of 3, three stable clusters predominated: root canal classification, endodontic instrumentation and treatment procedures, and imaging-based anatomical studies. The dense interconnections surrounding ‘micro-CT’ highlight its pivotal role as a methodological core in endodontic morphology research.

4. Discussion

Micro-CT has become a fundamental tool in in vitro endodontic research due to its ability to provide non-destructive, high-resolution, and three-dimensional visualization of internal dental anatomy.³ The bibliometric analysis conducted between 2000 and 2025 demonstrated a robust and sustained global increase in publications utilizing micro-CT for studies on root canal morphology, with notable geographic and thematic shifts over time.

The bibliometric pattern in Figure 2 demonstrates a three-phase evolution in micro-CT-based endodontic morphology research: (1) 2000–2009 – introduction and methodological validation, (2) 2010–2016 – expansion and scanner diffusion, and (3) 2017–2025 – consolidation and international collaboration. The initial decade showed low but steady growth, coinciding with micro-CT’s emergence as a research tool for dental hard-tissue imaging. Early publications emphasized validation and reproducibility compared with histologic and radiographic techniques. Limited scanner access and high costs restricted widespread use, yet the persistence of small-scale studies indicated that researchers recognized the technology’s methodological potential early on.^{7,21} After 2010, studies shifted from proving accuracy to applying micro-CT in complex anatomical and instrumentation research.^{22,23} The rising publication and citation curves confirm that micro-CT matured into a standard reference for evaluating shaping effects, canal curvature, and isthmus prevalence. This trend is consistent with the findings of Aksoy et al.¹⁵ who reported a similar inflection point around 2010, marking the transition from validation-based to application-oriented research. However, unlike that earlier analysis, the present study extended the time window to 2025 and reveals that global collaboration intensity and thematic diversity continued to expand rather than stabilize. Similarly, Alfadley et al.¹⁹ demonstrated that endodontic imaging research—especially in micro-CT and CBCT—has shifted toward integrative and data-driven methodologies, which aligns with the increased co-authorship and AI-related keyword emergence observed in our results. The plateau at higher publication volumes in Figure 2 suggests stable, durable integration rather than a transient surge. Multi-country collaboration networks (Brazil, USA, China, Türkiye, Germany, and Switzerland) indicate the field’s globalization,

Table 2. Country Contributions

Country/Region	Record Count	% of 409
Brazil	91	22%
USA	86	21%
Peoples R China	79	19%
Türkiye	44	10%
Germany	35	8%
Switzerland	34	8%
Italy	26	6%
Japan	24	5%
South Korea	19	4%

Counts are out of 409 records. Turkey and TÜRKIYE merged as “Türkiye”.

Table 3. Top 10 Journals by Publication Count

Journal	Record Count	% of 409
Journal of Endodontics	111	27.1%
International Endodontic Journal	57	13.9%
Clinical Oral Investigations	29	7.1%
BMC Oral Health	23	5.6%
Australian Endodontic Journal	17	4.2%
Archives of Oral Biology	12	2.9%
Scientific Reports	11	2.7%
Brazilian Oral Research	6	1.5%
Journal of Applied Oral Science	6	1.5%
Journal of Hard Tissue Biology	6	1.5%

Fig. 3. Co-authorship networks in micro-CT-based endodontic morphology research.

reflecting how knowledge diffusion and shared data pipelines have enhanced methodological consistency. The sustained citation growth implies that foundational works from the 2010s continued to influence later research, possibly due to integration with digital modeling.¹⁵

The country distribution highlights Brazil, the USA, and China as the primary contributors, jointly accounting for over 60% of all indexed records. This dominance suggests a mature and well-established research infrastructure within these nations, supported by consistent funding mechanisms, international collaborations, and academic institutions that prioritize high-impact endodontic research.^{24,25} Brazil's leadership position aligns with its strong endodontic research network centered around the University of São Paulo and the University of Minas Gerais, where structured postgraduate programs and micro-CT facilities have facilitated large-scale morphological investigations.²⁵ This institutional strength was further reflected in the productivity of leading Brazilian authors such as Versiani, Sousa-Neto, and Duarte, whose contributions dominate the field and reinforce the country's prominent role in endodontic research. Türkiye's emerging contribution, ranking fourth, underscores the growing capacity of middle-income regions to participate in high-resolution imaging research. The strong presence of European countries such as Germany, Switzerland, and Italy further highlights the global interconnectedness of the field. Overall, these data illustrate that endodontic imaging research has evolved from isolated national efforts into a transcontinental network of shared methodologies and co-authored investigations. The clustering pattern observed in the co-authorship maps corroborates this finding, showing that prolific authors frequently operate within dense, interlinked

Fig. 4. Cross-country collaboration networks in micro-CT-based endodontic morphology research.

Fig. 5. Node size, link thickness, distances, and colors represent keyword frequency, co-occurrence strength, relatedness, and clusters, respectively.

collaborative groups. The Brazilian-led cluster formed the core of the network, with strong internal cohesion and frequent cross-linkages to European and Asian authors. Peripheral but increasingly active contributors—particularly from Türkiye, China, and Korea—serve as bridges between regional research communities, enhancing global data integration and methodological exchange.

The journal distribution indicated that while endodontic-focused journals dominate the publication landscape, research on micro-CT and root canal morphology also showed substantial representation in broader dental science platforms. The Journal of Endodontics and International Endodontic Journal together accounted for over 40% of all indexed records, confirming their roles as core outlets for methodological and morphological investigations in endodontics. However, the presence of multidisciplinary journals such as Clinical Oral Investigations, BMC Oral Health, and Archives of Oral Biology reflected the cross-disciplinary relevance of micro-CT applications, extending beyond endodontics into restorative, anatomical, and biological research contexts. Similarly, the inclusion of Brazilian Oral Research and the Journal of Applied Oral Science highlighted the integration of endodontic imaging studies within national and general dentistry journals. This distribution suggested that micro-CT-based investigations have become an established methodological approach not only within endodontics but also across the wider field of dental research.

As observed in keyword co-occurrence network, core concepts related to root canal classification, endodontic instrumentation, and imaging-based anatomy were predominantly presented. Frequently recurring terms such as 'root canal configuration', 'curvature', 'instrumentation', and 'cone-beam computed tomography' indicated a research focus that balanced both morphological exploration and clinical applicability. Over recent years, new key terms—such as '3D reconstruction', 'deep learning', and 'digital imaging'—have begun to appear more frequently, reflecting the ongoing integration of computational analysis and artificial intelligence into imaging workflows.²⁶⁻²⁸ This trend highlighted a shift toward precision-based endodontics, where imaging data were utilized not only for structural assessment but also for predictive modeling, diagnosis, and treatment optimization. Future studies are expected to expand these interdisciplinary applications, combining advanced imaging with digital technologies to enhance reproducibility and clinical translation in dental research.²⁹

Cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) is another important imaging method used in endodontics for three-dimensional evaluation of root canal anatomy.^{30,31} Although CBCT provides valuable clinical information, its lower image resolution compared

to micro-CT limits its use for detailed morphological studies.³² However, CBCT remains essential for in vivo imaging and clinical decision-making. In recent years, studies combining CBCT and micro-CT have shown that both techniques can complement each other—micro-CT offering precise laboratory data and CBCT providing practical clinical visualization. Together, these technologies support better diagnosis, treatment planning, and understanding of root canal morphology in both research and clinical practice.^{7,33}

Although this analysis provided an in-depth look of global publication trends, several methodological limitations were noted. In this study, the data source was limited to the WoSCC and SCI-Expanded publications, which were selected for their high-quality indexing of peer-reviewed journals and compatibility with bibliometric software.³⁴ Consequently, relevant publications indexed in other databases might have been missed. These exclusions could lead to minor discrepancies in country- or author-level output. Nevertheless, the use of WoSCC and SCI expanded ensures standardized citation tracking, reliable metadata, and methodological consistency, which together strengthen the validity of the present bibliometric assessment.³⁵ Future research should focus on expanding the integration of micro-CT data with advanced computational methods such as artificial intelligence and digital modeling. Comparative analyses using multi-modal imaging can further validate measurement consistency.

Micro-computed tomography has evolved from a validation instrument into a foundational technology that underpins modern endodontic research. The steady global increase in publications, broad international collaboration, and thematic diversification confirm its sustained scientific and clinical relevance. As the field advances, continued standardization, data sharing, and integration with artificial intelligence are expected to define the next phase of innovation—bridging anatomical insight with clinical application and setting new benchmarks for precision in endodontic science.

5. Conclusion

This bibliometric analysis demonstrates the sustained global growth and methodological maturation of micro-CT-based research in root canal morphology over the past 25 years. The findings highlight the central role of micro-CT as a precise, non-destructive imaging technique that has advanced both anatomical understanding and experimental standardization in endodontics. Ongoing integration with computational tools, digital imaging, and artificial intelligence is expected to further strengthen the reproducibility, accuracy, and clinical translation of future research in this field.

References

- Mamat R, Nik Abdul Ghani NR. The Complexity of the Root Canal Anatomy and Its Influence on Root Canal Debridement in the Apical Region: A Review. *Cureus*. 2023;15(11):e49024.
- Pertek Hatipoğlu F, Magat G, Karobari MI, Madarati AA, Tulegenova I, Hatipoğlu Ö, et al. Root and canal configurations of maxillary first premolars in 22 countries using two classification systems: a multinational cross-sectional study. *Sci Rep*. 2025;15(1):19290.
- Lavanya A, Ali S, Tewari RK. Micro-computed tomography in endodontics. *J Oral Res Rev*. 2023;15(1):80-86.
- Karobari MI, Batul R, Khan M, Patil SR, Basheer SN, Rezallah NNF, et al. Micro computed tomography (Micro-CT) characterization of root and root canal morphology of mandibular first premolars: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMC Oral Health*. 2024;24(1):1.
- Rhodes JS, Ford TRP, Lynch JA, Liepins PJ, Curtis RV. Micro-computed tomography: a new tool for experimental endodontology. *Int Endod J*. 1999;32(3):165-170.
- Nielsen RB, Alyassin AM, Peters DD, Carnes DL, Lancaster J. Microcomputed tomography: an advanced system for detailed endodontic research. *J Endod*. 1995;21(11):561-568.
- Swain MV, Xue J. State of the art of micro-CT applications in dental research. *Int J Oral Sci*. 2009;1(4):177-188.
- Peters OA, Schönenberger K, Laib A. Effects of four Ni-Ti preparation techniques on root canal geometry assessed by micro computed tomography. *Int Endod J*. 2001;34(3):221-230.
- Yang G, Yuan G, Yun X, Zhou X, Liu B, Wu H. Effects of two nickel-titanium instrument systems, Mtwo versus ProTaper Universal, on root canal geometry assessed by micro-computed tomography. *J Endod*. 2011;37(10):1412-1416.
- Alak SG, Keleş A, Keskin C, Martins JNR, Versiani MA. Age-related changes in the morphology of the root canal system of mandibular first molars: a micro-CT study. *Clin Oral Investig*. 2023;27(8):4667-4675.
- Wolf TG, Rempapi T, Armogida NG, Spagnuolo G, Waber AL. Micro-computed tomographic analysis of the morphology of maxillary canines. *Sci Rep*. 2025;15(1):4111.
- Nurulaqmar Iwani S, Kamaruzaman M, Jawami AA. Microcomputed tomography (micro-CT) analysis of apical mandibular premolar in relation to clinical sign presentation: an in vitro study. *Saudi Dent J*. 2024;36(1):129-133.
- Lin X, Fu Y, Ren G, Yang X, Duan W, Chen Y, et al. Micro-computed tomography-guided artificial intelligence for pulp cavity and tooth segmentation on cone-beam computed tomography. *J Endod*. 2021;47(12):1933-1941.
- Setzer FC, Li J, Khan AA. The use of artificial intelligence in endodontics. *J Dent Res*. 2024;103(9):853-862.
- Aksoy U, Küçük M, Versiani MA, Orhan K. Publication trends in micro-CT endodontic research: a bibliometric analysis over a 25-year period. *Int Endod J*. 2021;54(3):343-353.
- Ghavami-Lahiji M, Davaloo RT, Tajziehchi G, Shams P. Micro-computed tomography in preventive and restorative dental research: a review. *Imaging Sci Dent*. 2021;51(4):341.
- Donthu N, Kumar S, Mukherjee D, Pandey N, Lim WM. How to conduct a bibliometric analysis: an overview and guidelines. *J Bus Res*. 2021;133:285-297.
- Chen C, Song M. Visualizing a field of research: a methodology of systematic scientometric reviews. *PLoS One*. 2019;14(10):e0223994.
- Alfadley A, Alfouzan K, Gopinathan PA, Ul Haq I, Alrumi FA, Alahmari AH, et al. Mapping of global research in endodontics from 2004 to 2023: a bibliometric analysis. *Cureus*. 2024;16(12):e75694.
- Montazeri A, Mohammadi S, Hesari PM, Ghaemi M, Riazhi H, Sheikh-Mobarakeh Z. Preliminary guideline for reporting bibliometric reviews of the biomedical literature (BIBLIO): a minimum requirements. *Syst Rev*. 2023;12(1):239.
- Dowker SEP, Davis GR, Elliott JC. X-ray microtomography. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod*. 1997;83(4):510-516.
- Verma P, Love RM. A micro-CT study of the mesiobuccal root canal morphology of the maxillary first molar tooth. *Int Endod J*. 2011;44(3):210-217.
- Ordinola-Zapata R, Bramante CM, Villas-Boas MH, Cavenago BC, Duarte MH, Versiani MA. Morphologic micro-computed tomography analysis of mandibular premolars with three root canals. *J Endod*. 2013;39(9):1130-1135.
- Pedrazzi V, Dias KRHC, Rode SM. Oral health in Brazil – Part II: Dental Specialty Centers (CEOs). *Braz Oral Res*. 2008;22(Suppl 1):18-23.
- Melgaço-Costa JLB, Martins RC, Ferreira EF, Paulino Ribeiro-Sobrinho A. Endodontic output in public healthcare under different instrumentation techniques: a quantitative and qualitative study. *Pesqui Bras Odontopediatria Clin Integr*. 2021;21.

26. Lu W, Yu X, Li Y, Cao Y, Chen Y, Hua F. Artificial Intelligence-Related Dental Research: Bibliometric and Altmetric Analysis. *Int Dent J*. 2025;75(1):166-175.
27. Magat G, Altındağ A, Pertek Hatipoğlu F, Hatipoğlu Ö, Bayrakdar İS, Çelik O, et al. Automatic deep learning detection of overhanging restorations in bitewing radiographs. *Dentomaxillofac Radiol*. 2024;53(7):468-477.
28. Aljawhar AM, Ibrahim N, Abdul Aziz A, Ahmed HMA, Azami NH. Micro-computed tomographic evaluation of root and canal anatomy of maxillary first premolars in Iraqi sub-population. *Sci Rep*. 2025;15(1):10821.
29. Lai G, Dunlap C, Gluskin A, Nehme WB, Azim AA. Artificial intelligence in endodontics. *J Calif Dent Assoc*. 2023;51(1).
30. Pertek Hatipoğlu F, Mağat G, Hatipoğlu Ö, Taha N, Alfirjani S, Abidin IZ, et al. Assessment of the prevalence of middle mesial canal in mandibular first molar: a multinational cross-sectional study with meta-analysis. *J Endod*. 2023;49(5):549-558.
31. Almeida JC, Candemil AP, Bertolini GR, Souza-Gabriel AE, Cruz-Filho AM, Sousa-Neto MD, et al. Cone-beam computed tomographic evaluation of the root canal anatomy of the lower premolars and molars in a Brazilian sub-population. *Imaging Sci Dent*. 2023;53(1):77-83.
32. Michetti J, Maret D, Mallet JP, Diemer F. Validation of cone beam computed tomography as a tool to explore root canal anatomy. *J Endod*. 2010;36(7):1187-1190.
33. Chugal N, Assad H, Markovic D, Mallya SM. Applying the American Association of Endodontists and American Academy of Oral and Maxillofacial Radiology guidelines for cone-beam computed tomography prescription. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 2024;155(1):48-58.
34. Birkle C, Pendlebury DA, Schnell J, Adams J. Web of Science as a data source for research on scientific and scholarly activity. *Quant Sci Stud*. 2020;1(1):363-376.
35. Prancutè R. Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus: the titans of bibliographic information in today's academic world. *Publications*. 2021;9(1):12.

How to cite this article:

Başar Ö. Global Trends in Micro-CT Studies of Root Canal Morphology: A 25-Year Bibliometric Analysis. *J Endod Restor Dent*. 2026; 4(1):1-6.
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.18585140

AI Declaration

No generative AI used for writing/analysis/figures. — AI-assisted language editing was used only to improve grammar and clarity. All data collection, screening, analysis, visualization, and interpretation were performed manually and independently verified by the author. No AI tools were used to generate, analyze, or interpret data.

Conflict of Interest

All authors declare no conflicts of interest.

CRedit Author Statement

Ö. B. : Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization

Data Availability Statement

No new data were created or analyzed.

Ethics Approval

Not applicable.

Funding

No external funding.

Original Article

Performance Comparison of Large Language Models in Dentistry: A Focus on Restorative Dentistry Using Turkish Specialty Exam Questions

Muhammed Baytar ^a, Fatma Pertek Hatipoğlu ^b

^a Department of Restorative Dentistry, Recep Tayyip Erdoğan University, Rize, Türkiye.

^b Department of Endodontics, Recep Tayyip Erdoğan University, Rize, Türkiye.

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 17.09.2025
Completion of First Review: 25.12.2025
Accepted: 29.01.2026
Published: 01.03.2026

KEYWORDS

Artificial Intelligence
Dental Education
Large Language Models
Restorative Dentistry

CORRESPONDENCE

Muhammed Baytar
Department of Restorative Dentistry, Recep
Tayyip Erdoğan University, Rize, Türkiye.
E-mail: muhammed.baytar@erdogan.edu.tr

CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

Large language models may support dental education and clinical knowledge reinforcement. Model-specific differences in accuracy, speed, and response depth highlight the importance of selecting appropriate systems based on educational or clinical objectives rather than relying on a single tool.

ABSTRACT

Objectives: This study aimed to comparatively evaluate the accuracy, response time, and content length of five large language models (LLMs), ChatGPT-4o, ChatGPT-o3-mini, Deepseek-v3, Google Gemini 2.0 Flash, and Microsoft Copilot, based on restorative dentistry questions from the Turkish Dental Specialty Exam (DUS).

Materials and Methods: A total of 100 multiple-choice questions from the restorative dentistry sections of the DUS (2016–2024) were presented to each LLM model in Turkish under standardized testing conditions. Model performance was assessed based on three primary metrics: answer accuracy, response generation time, and content length (word count). Temporal consistency was evaluated by re-submitting a 10% sample after two weeks. Statistical analyses were conducted to compare differences among the models.

Results: ChatGPT-o3-mini achieved the highest accuracy (96%), followed by ChatGPT-4o (90%), Deepseek-v3 (88%), and both Gemini and Copilot (85%). Microsoft Copilot was the fastest model (median: 3.19 s), while Deepseek-v3 was the slowest (median: 25.64 s). Google Gemini 2.0 Flash produced the longest responses (median: 218 words), whereas Microsoft Copilot generated the shortest (median: 34 words).

Conclusion: LLMs demonstrate promising potential for supporting dental education, particularly in restorative domains. Among the evaluated models, ChatGPT-o3-mini showed the highest overall accuracy, suggesting its relative suitability for knowledge-based tasks in dentistry. However, performance varied by model and topic, indicating that no single system is universally superior. Model selection should be guided by the intended application, whether speed, depth, or accuracy is prioritized. The use of standardized specialty exam questions offers a reliable framework for benchmarking LLM performance in domain-specific contexts.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the rapid advancements in Large Language Models (LLMs) have led to significant transformations in healthcare services, with widespread applications in clinical decision support systems, diagnostic processes, patient monitoring, and access to medical information.^{1,2} These systems offer advantages such as accuracy, speed, and accessibility, providing substantial support to healthcare professionals and facilitating clinical workflows.^{3,4} The opportunities presented by LLMs are increasingly being adopted in the field of dentistry as well. Owing to their capacity to respond to knowledge-based dental queries, LLMs are being recognized as effective tools in both educational settings and treatment planning.⁵⁻⁷ These models assist in decision-making processes such as clinical guidance, material selection, and case evaluation, and hold considerable potential particularly in restorative dentistry, which is a practice-intensive domain.^{8,9}

Among the advanced artificial intelligence models developed in recent times, ChatGPT-4o, ChatGPT-o3-mini, Deepseek-v3, Google Gemini 2.0 Flash, and Microsoft Copilot stand out by offering various advantages in knowledge-intensive fields such as dentistry.^{6,7,10} ChatGPT-4o, with its text-input performance and high accuracy rates, offers broad application potential, while ChatGPT-o3-mini is notable for its compact structure and ability to generate fast and accurate responses. Deepseek-v3 tends to produce detailed and explanatory answers, particularly in the generation of scientific content and the communication of technical information. Google Gemini 2.0 Flash, on the other hand, distinguishes itself through its high response speed and user-friendly interface. Microsoft Copilot provides a distinct user

experience by producing concise and focused answers. A systematic evaluation of these models' performance in responding to dental knowledge-based queries may contribute to a better understanding of their potential in both educational and clinical contexts.

Although some studies in the current literature have evaluated the performance of LLM models in the field of dentistry, most focus on a single model or are limited to superficial comparisons among a small number of systems.⁶⁻⁸ In particular, there is a notable lack of comprehensive studies comparing advanced models in terms of their performance across specific subcategories of dental knowledge, including anatomical structures, microbiology, restorative materials, therapeutic treatments, and aesthetic Technologies.¹⁰⁻¹² Moreover, the absence of systematic analyses evaluating these models based on criteria such as response accuracy, generation time, and content scope hinders the reliable assessment of their potential for clinical and educational applications.^{9,13} This limitation makes it difficult to objectively understand the strengths and weaknesses of each model and to confidently integrate them into clinical practice. In this context, a comparative evaluation of the responses provided by these LLMs to dental knowledge-based queries—in terms of accuracy, speed, and comprehensiveness—holds the potential to fill a critical gap in the literature.¹⁴

This study aims to comparatively evaluate the performance of the artificial intelligence models ChatGPT-4o, ChatGPT-o3-mini, Deepseek-v3, Google Gemini 2.0 Flash, and Microsoft Copilot in terms of their knowledge level, response time, and content scope in the field of dentistry. The models were analyzed based on

objective criteria including accuracy rates, response generation times, and content lengths. Additionally, their performance was assessed across various subcategories of dental knowledge. To date, no study in the literature has examined such a wide range of LLMs while simultaneously providing an in-depth evaluation of dental knowledge domains. In this regard, the study is expected to reveal which LLMs are more reliable and efficient for use in dental education and clinical decision support systems.

The null hypothesis tested in this study is that there is no statistically significant difference among the models, ChatGPT-4o, ChatGPT-o3-mini, Deepseek-v3, Google Gemini 2.0 Flash, and Microsoft Copilot, in terms of the accuracy, response time, and content scope of their answers to dentistry-specific questions.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Design

This comparative observational study was designed to evaluate the performance of five advanced large language models, ChatGPT-4o, ChatGPT-o3-mini, Deepseek-v3, Google Gemini 2.0 Flash, and Microsoft Copilot, in answering dentistry-specific knowledge-based questions. The models' responses were assessed using objective performance criteria including accuracy, response time, and content length. Additionally, the consistency of responses over time was analyzed to determine the temporal reliability of each model.

2.2. A priori Power Analysis

A priori power analysis was conducted to justify the sample size for between-model accuracy comparisons. Because each multiple-choice question (MCQ) was evaluated by all five LLMs, accuracy comparisons were based on a paired design at the question level. Accordingly, statistical power was primarily determined by the proportion of discordant responses between model pairs rather than by marginal accuracy alone.

Assuming a two-sided significance level of 0.05, a total of 100 paired MCQs provides approximately 80% power to detect absolute differences in accuracy of approximately 10–12% between models under plausible discordance rates of 15–20%, using McNemar-type tests for paired proportions. When accounting for multiple pairwise comparisons, the minimum detectable difference increases to approximately 15%. These effect sizes were considered meaningful for benchmarking model performance in an educational and clinical context.

Category-level analyses were planned as secondary and exploratory due to limited numbers of MCQs in some domains, and no separate power calculations were performed for these subgroup analyses.

2.3. Model versioning and inference settings

All LLMs were evaluated using their publicly available web-based interfaces during a defined testing window (January–February 2025). Model versions and access tiers were recorded at the time of evaluation. ChatGPT-4o and ChatGPT-o3-mini were accessed via a paid subscription tier, whereas Google Gemini 2.0 Flash and Microsoft Copilot were accessed through their standard publicly available interfaces. Deepseek-v3 was accessed via its official web interface.

No custom system prompts were used. All queries were submitted using the default chat interface of each platform, and responses were generated using platform-default inference parameters. When model-specific generation settings were not user-adjustable via the interface, they were assumed to be fixed at their default values. All evaluations were conducted using the standard default response mode provided by each platform at the time of testing.

All models were prompted with identical user inputs. During testing, no safety-related refusals or content blocks were observed for the included multiple-choice questions; all models provided a substantive response to each prompt.

2.4. Data Source and Question Categories

The dataset consisted of 100 MCQs derived from Restorative Dentistry sections of the Dental Specialty Examination (DUS), administered in Türkiye by the Student Selection and Placement Center (OSYM) between 2016 and 2024. Each DUS exam comprises 120 questions, including 80 clinical science items and 40 basic science items. Restorative Dentistry is one of the eight clinical science disciplines represented in the clinical component, typically contributing 10 questions per exam.

The questions were selected to ensure broad coverage of key domains within restorative dental knowledge. In order to facilitate detailed analysis, each question was classified into one of six major subcategories of dental knowledge based on content:

1. Anatomical Structures and Oral Environment
2. Dental Caries and Other Lesions
3. Restorative Materials and Application Techniques
4. Therapeutic and Preventive Procedures
5. Aesthetic and Advanced Technologies
6. Microbiology and Oral Biofilm

Sample questions for each category along with their English equivalents are provided in Table 1, while the complete list of questions is included in the Supplemental File.

2.5. Testing Procedure of AI Models

All 100 questions were submitted to each AI model by the same operator (M.B) under standardized conditions to minimize operator bias. The questions were input in Turkish, reflecting their original language in the DUS exams. The models were not tested concurrently but sequentially in a controlled testing environment to avoid temporal or server-based variations that might influence performance.

Each model's response to each question was evaluated using the following three core metrics:

Accuracy: Binary scoring (correct/incorrect) based on the model's ability to select or generate the correct answer as per the official DUS key.

Response Time: Measured in milliseconds using a digital stopwatch initiated the moment a question was submitted and stopped once a complete answer was received.

Response Length: Calculated as the total word count of the generated response using Microsoft Word's word count tool.

All responses and performance metrics were recorded systematically, and comparative analyses were conducted.

2.6. Response Consistency and Reliability Testing

To evaluate the temporal consistency of the language models, a subset of 10 questions (10% of the total dataset) was re-submitted to each model exactly two weeks after the initial testing phase. The second-round responses were compared with the originals in terms of both accuracy (correctness of answer) and content stability (response time and word count).

2.7. Ethical Considerations

As this study did not involve human participants, patient data, or clinical intervention, ethical approval was not required. However, all data sources used (DUS questions) are publicly available through the official website of ÖSYM (<https://www.osym.gov.tr>), and were used solely for academic research purposes.

Table 1. The presentation of two different question examples and their answers from each category.

Operative Dentistry Topics	Examples of questions	Choices
Anatomical Structures and Oral Environment	What is the name of the unmineralized dentin layer adjacent to the odontoblast cells in the pulp?	A) Mantle dentin B) Circumpulpal dentin C) Secondary dentin D) Primary dentin E) Predentin
Anatomical Structures and Oral Environment	What is the name of the optical image formed by the arrangement of prism groups in different directions to prevent enamel fracture?	A) Retzius line B) Hunter-Schreger band C) Enamel lamella D) Perikymata E) Enamel tuft
Dental Caries and Other Lesions	Which of the following is not one of the layers of an initial enamel caries lesion?	A) Dark zone B) Body of the lesion C) Translucent zone D) Infected layer E) Surface layer
Dental Caries and Other Lesions	Which of the following is not a risk factor for the development of root surface caries in elderly individuals?	A) Use of medications that cause dry mouth B) Cariogenic diet C) Increased salivary flow rate D) Gingival recession E) Use of partial dentures
Restorative Materials and Application Techniques	Which monomer is added to composite resins to reduce or control viscosity?	A) TEGDMA B) Bis-GMA C) UDMA D) 10-MDP E) 4-META
Restorative Materials and Application Techniques	Which component in composite resins binds the organic and inorganic phases together and ensures stress distribution?	A) Camphorquinone B) Tertiary amine C) Triethylene glycol dimethacrylate D) Barium glass E) Silane
Therapeutic and Preventive Treatments	Which of the following is used in the microabrasion procedure for the treatment of tooth discoloration?	A) Orthophosphoric acid B) Maleic acid C) Citric acid D) Hydrochloric acid E) Hydrofluoric acid
Therapeutic and Preventive Treatments	In which of the following conditions is treatment with the resin infiltration technique not recommended?	A) Fluorosis cases B) Cavitated root surface caries C) Hypomineralization cases D) Initial interproximal caries E) White spot lesions
Aesthetic and Advanced Technologies	Which of the following lasers is the least likely to be used in the treatment of dentin hypersensitivity?	A) CO ₂ laser B) Argon laser C) Er:YAG laser D) Er,Cr:YSGG laser E) Nd:YAG laser
Aesthetic and Advanced Technologies	Which optical property is defined as reflecting short-wavelength light as blue and transmitting long-wavelength light as yellow/red?	A) Fluorescence B) Translucency C) Opalescence D) Opacity E) Transparency
Microbiology and Oral Biofilm	Which of the following bacteria is not a member of the Mitis group streptococci?	A) Streptococcus sanguinis B) Streptococcus infantis C) Streptococcus peroris D) Streptococcus oralis E) Streptococcus cristatus
Microbiology and Oral Biofilm	Which of the following microorganisms does not belong to the mutans group of oral streptococci?	A) Streptococcus salivarius B) Streptococcus sobrinus C) Streptococcus ferus D) Streptococcus ratti E) Streptococcus criceti

The questions submitted to the chatbots were in Turkish without an English translation. However, the table has been translated into English for the readers' convenience.

2.7. Statistical Analysis

All statistical analyses were performed using Jamovi software (Version 2.3.28), with a significance threshold set at $p < 0.05$. To compare the overall accuracy rates among the five LLMs, the Cochran's Q test was applied, and McNemar's test was used for pairwise comparisons of correct versus incorrect responses. Differences in response time and word count across models were evaluated using the Kruskal-Wallis test, followed by Dwass-Steel-

Critchlow-Fligner post hoc tests to determine pairwise significance. For domain-specific performance, accuracy across subcategories of restorative dentistry (e.g., anatomical structures, microbiology, materials) was assessed using the Chi-squared test. Additionally, to assess the temporal consistency and reliability of the models, 10% of the questions were re-submitted two weeks after the initial testing. In this phase, Cohen's Kappa was used to measure agreement in accuracy between time points, while

Fig. 1. Accuracy Comparison of Large Language Models in Dentistry

Fig. 2. Response Time Distribution Among AI Models

Concordance Correlation Coefficients (CCC) were calculated to assess consistency in response time and word count.

3. Results

The performance comparison of LLMs in terms of accuracy, response time, and word count revealed statistically significant differences across the evaluated systems (Table 2). Accuracy varied among the models, with ChatGPT-o3-mini achieving the highest proportion of correct responses (96%), which was significantly greater than Deepseek-v3 (88%), Google Gemini 2.0 Flash (85%), and Microsoft Copilot (85%) ($p = 0.011$). ChatGPT-4o demonstrated an intermediate accuracy level (90%), with no statistically significant difference from ChatGPT-o3-mini (Fig. 1).

Regarding response time, Microsoft Copilot responded the fastest, with a median time of 3.19 seconds, significantly lower than all other models ($p < 0.001$). Google Gemini 2.0 Flash and ChatGPT-o3-mini followed with similarly low response times (7.19 s and 7.54 s, respectively), whereas ChatGPT-4o (14.5 s) and particularly Deepseek-v3 (25.64 s) were significantly slower (Fig. 2).

In terms of word count, Google Gemini 2.0 Flash produced the most verbose responses (median: 218 words), significantly higher than all other models ($p < 0.001$). In contrast, Microsoft Copilot generated the shortest responses (median: 34 words), while ChatGPT-4o (144.5 words) and Deepseek-v3 (135.5 words) had comparable outputs. ChatGPT-o3-mini generated a significantly lower word count (92.5 words) than ChatGPT-4o and Deepseek-v3 but remained above Microsoft Copilot (Fig. 3).

Table 3 presents the accuracy rates of different LLMs across various dental knowledge categories. Overall, ChatGPT-o3-mini demonstrated the highest accuracy across most categories, achieving 100% accuracy in microbiology, restorative materials, therapeutic treatments, and aesthetic technologies. ChatGPT-4o and Deepseek-v3 also performed well, particularly in anatomical structures (88% and 92%, respectively) and restorative materials (94% and 91%). In contrast, Google Gemini 2.0 Flash and Microsoft Copilot showed lower accuracy in anatomical structures (79% and 75%) and restorative materials (94% and 85%), suggesting a

relative weakness in these areas. Despite these differences, the p -values indicate no statistically significant differences among the models, implying comparable performance across most domains.

To evaluate temporal reliability, 10% of the questions were re-submitted to each model two weeks after initial testing. Accuracy agreement, assessed using Cohen's Kappa, was perfect ($\kappa = 1.000$) for ChatGPT-4o, ChatGPT-o3-mini, and Deepseek, indicating almost perfect reliability ($\kappa \geq 0.81$).¹⁵ Copilot showed substantial agreement ($\kappa = 0.737$), while Gemini demonstrated only moderate consistency ($\kappa = 0.545$). Response time and word count stability were evaluated using Concordance Correlation Coefficients (CCC). ChatGPT-4o (0.232, 0.769), o3-mini (-0.018, 0.643), and Deepseek (0.043, 0.567) exhibited moderate-to-strong concordance ($CCC \geq 0.40$), while Gemini and Copilot showed poor agreement ($CCC < 0.25$).¹⁶ (Table 4, Fig. 4).

4. Discussion

This study is among the first to systematically evaluate multiple LLMs using national specialty exam questions in restorative dentistry. The findings reveal that ChatGPT-o3-mini achieved the highest accuracy, while Copilot demonstrated the fastest response times and Gemini produced the most verbose outputs. These findings suggest that LLMs should not be evaluated through a singular definition of the "best system," but rather through a context-dependent approach that considers the suitability of different models for different tasks. Indeed, it was observed that models with higher content accuracy sometimes demonstrated slower response times, whereas models that generated faster responses tended to lag in content depth and coherence.^{14,17} This underscores the need for purpose-driven model selection in application scenarios such as clinical decision support systems, patient education, preclinical learning, and the development of digital instructional materials.

The findings of this study align with the analysis conducted by Sallam, et al.¹⁸, who reported that models like ChatGPT, Gemini, and Copilot exhibited inconsistent performance across different dental subfields. While these models showed high accuracy in certain areas, they sometimes produced content-deficient

Table 2. Comparative Performance of AI Models in Accuracy, Response Time, and Word Count

	ChatGPT-4o	ChatGPT-o3-mini	Deepseek- v3	Google Gemini 2.0 Flash	Microsoft Copilot	p-value
Accuracy						
True	90 (90%) ^{AB}	96 (96%) ^A	88 (88%) ^B	85 (85%) ^B	85 (85%) ^B	0.011 ¹
False	10 (10%) ^{AB}	4 (4.0%) ^A	12 (12%) ^B	15 (15%) ^B	15 (15%) ^B	
Response Time (second)	14.5 (4.58-34.49) ^C	7.535 (3.52-33.55) ^A	25.64 (11.84-53.67) ^D	7.19 (4.91-12.19) ^A	3.185 (1.95-10.07) ^B	<0.001 ²
Word counts	144.5 (28-315) ^B	92.5 (29-315) ^C	135.5 (34-286) ^B	218 (87-341) ^A	34 (11-103) ^D	<0.001 ²

N (%), Median (Min-Max), ¹ Cochran's Q test, McNemar Test for pairwise comparisons, ² Kruskal Wallis test, Dwass-Steel-Critchlow-Fligner pairwise comparisons. Different uppercase superscript letters indicate significant difference ($p < 0.05$).

Fig. 3. Word Count Analysis of Model-Generated Answers

Fig. 4. Temporal Reliability of AI Model Responses Based on Cohen's Kappa

responses, particularly in microbiology and materials science domains.¹⁸ Similarly, a comparative evaluation by Reyhan, et al.¹⁹ emphasized intra-model response fluctuations and reproducibility issues, highlighting the need for careful consideration of validity and security, especially in exam-based assessments. Llorente de Pedro, et al.²⁰ further support these concerns, demonstrating notable inconsistencies in ChatGPT's responses to clinically structured endodontic questions, particularly under repeated prompt scenarios, thereby stressing the importance of test-retest reliability in educational and certification contexts. In conclusion, this study provides valuable empirical evidence toward understanding the suitability of advanced LLMs in clinical and pedagogical contexts within dentistry. Furthermore, identifying the strengths and limitations of different models lays a foundational framework for the development of future specialized dental LLMs.

When evaluated within this context, the low accuracy rates of LLMs in responding to basic science questions indicate that these systems still possess limited representational capacity in knowledge domains based on visual and biological data.²⁰ In particular, the decline in accuracy observed in disciplines such as anatomical structures, oral histology, and microbiology may stem from the underrepresentation of such content in the training datasets of LLMs. This outcome is consistent with the findings of Nguyen, et al.¹⁴, who also highlighted the limited capacity of LLMs to generate accurate responses in dental scenarios requiring visual-spatial reasoning.

Moreover, the variability in model performance across different knowledge subcategories underscores the need to move beyond aggregated accuracy scores and adopt a topic-based performance mapping approach. For instance, the relatively high accuracy demonstrated by ChatGPT-o3-mini should not be viewed merely

as superiority, but rather as a reflection of its broader and clinically optimized training corpus. Batool, et al.²¹ also reported that such models tend to outperform others in medical content generation due to their enhanced compatibility with health-related terminology. Conversely, the lower accuracy scores observed in models like Google Gemini 2.0 Flash and Microsoft Copilot may be attributable not only to differences in training data but also to the primary design purposes of these systems. As these models are primarily developed for general-purpose productivity and assistant functions, their ability to deliver in-depth content in specialized technical domains (e.g., dental pharmacology, biomaterials classification) appears to be inherently limited. Overall, the findings reinforce the principle that "no single model fits all tasks." As the content, depth, and format of dental knowledge domains vary, it becomes clear that LLMs must be evaluated and selected according to a task-specific approach. This insight is not only a technical consideration but also suggests that the integration of LLM into dental education must be structured in alignment with pedagogical strategies.¹⁹

The differences observed in response times among LLMs are largely attributed to technical factors such as the architectural design of the systems, the volume of data used during training, and the underlying server infrastructures.^{14,20,22} According to the study data, Microsoft Copilot achieved the shortest median response time (3.19 seconds), positioning it as the fastest model in this regard. Its tendency to produce relatively shorter and less context-rich responses may reduce processing load and thereby enhance speed. Similarly, Google Gemini 2.0 Flash and ChatGPT-o3-mini also demonstrated short response times, making them particularly advantageous for time-sensitive applications such as bedside decision support and urgent clinical guidance.²³

In contrast, Deepseek-v3 exhibited the longest response time in the study (median: 25.64 seconds), making it the slowest model overall. This may be attributed to the model's architecture, which

Table 3. Accuracy Rates of AI Models Across Different Operative Dentistry Knowledge Categories

Characteristics	ChatGPT-4o	ChatGPT-o3-mini	Deepseek- v3	Google Gemini 2.0 Flash	Microsoft Copilot
Anatomical Structures and Oral Environment N = 24 (24%)	21 (88%)	23 (96%)	22 (92%)	19 (79%)	18 (75%)
Dental Caries and Other Lesions N = 19 (19%)	16 (84%)	16 (84%)	17 (89%)	16 (84%)	16 (84%)
Microbiology and Oral Biofilm N = 4 (4.0%)	3 (75%)	4 (100%)	3 (75%)	3 (75%)	3 (75%)
Restorative Materials and Application Techniques N = 33 (33%)	31 (94%)	33 (100%)	30 (91%)	31 (94%)	28 (85%)
Therapeutic and Preventive Treatments N = 9 (9.0%)	9 (100%)	9 (100%)	7 (78%)	7 (78%)	9 (100%)
Aesthetic and Advanced Technologies N = 11 (11%)	10 (91%)	11 (100%)	9 (82%)	9 (82%)	11 (100%)
p-value	0.550 ¹	0.160 ¹	0.590 ¹	0.420 ¹	0.320 ¹

¹ Chi-squared test

Table 4. Test–Retest Reliability of Language Models Based on Repeated Submissions

LLMs	Accuracy	Response Time (second)	Word counts
chat gpt 4o	1.000	0.232	0.769
chat gpt o3-mini	1.000	-0.018	0.643
deepseek	1.000	0.043	0.567
gemini	0.545	0.108	-0.001
co pilot	0.737	-0.003	0.217

Ten previously asked questions were re-submitted after two weeks. Accuracy was measured using Kappa statistics, while response time and word count stability were analyzed via concordance correlation coefficients.

appears to prioritize the generation of more detailed and comprehensive responses, thereby increasing processing time. However, the relationship between response time and content quality is not linear. Notably, Microsoft Copilot, the fastest model, demonstrated the lowest accuracy. Conversely, ChatGPT-o3-mini stood out with both a high accuracy rate and a balanced response time. These findings indicate that speed alone is not a reliable indicator of quality, and that content accuracy should be prioritized, especially in educational and clinical contexts.^{14,20,24} In conclusion, it is evident that selecting LLMs requires establishing an optimal balance between speed and content quality.

When comparing the performance of artificial intelligence models in terms of response length, significant differences were observed among the systems. Google Gemini 2.0 Flash stood out by generating the longest and most comprehensive responses, with an average of 218 words, whereas Microsoft Copilot produced notably brief outputs, averaging only 34 words, thus offering minimal content generation.^{19,25} Longer responses may provide advantages in contexts that require detailed clinical explanations, the conveyance of theoretical knowledge, or the presentation of alternative approaches in educational settings.²⁶ However, increased text length does not necessarily equate to higher quality.²⁷ Indeed, some studies have reported that excessively long responses may lead to redundant information or ambiguity, thereby complicating decision-making processes.²⁸ In this context, models such as ChatGPT-4o and Deepseek-v3, which produced moderately lengthy outputs, demonstrated a balanced performance by delivering content that was both informative and concise.^{29,30} Although Google Gemini 2.0 Flash generated lengthy responses in terms of word count, its relatively lower accuracy rates suggest that verbosity does not always translate into meaningful information.³¹ While comprehensive explanations may be preferred in educational environments, shorter, more direct, and high-accuracy content tends to be prioritized in clinical applications where time is limited.³² Therefore, response length should not be regarded as an isolated indicator of quality; rather, it must be considered alongside context, accuracy, and the specific needs of the end user.³³

When evaluating the performance of LLMs across dentistry-specific subdomains, significant differences in accuracy among categories become apparent.¹⁹ In particular, models demonstrate higher overall accuracy in more clinically oriented and application-based domains such as restorative materials, therapeutic procedures, and esthetic technologies.³¹ This can be attributed to the greater representation of such topics in training datasets and the clearer, more well-defined nature of the questions in these domains.³¹ Similarly, the study by Lafourcade, et al.³⁴ in 2025, demonstrated that ChatGPT models exhibited higher accuracy and consistency in clinically oriented domains such as restorative dentistry and endodontics. In contrast, markedly lower accuracy rates were observed for models such as Google Gemini 2.0 Flash and Microsoft Copilot in foundational science categories like anatomical structures and microbiology.²⁸ These domains often involve complex terminology, require visual content, and demand interdisciplinary knowledge—factors that can challenge purely text-based models.²⁹ On the other hand, the strong performance of ChatGPT-o3-mini and ChatGPT-4o in these areas suggests that

their training on more comprehensive and medically focused datasets provides a significant advantage.³² These differences among LLMs clearly underscore the necessity of careful model selection based on the intended context of use.³³ As emphasized by Ong, et al.³², selecting the most appropriate model for specific scenarios, such as education or clinical decision support, is crucial for achieving optimal outcomes.

One of the major strengths of this study lies in its systematic comparison of five contemporary artificial intelligence models across various dentistry-specific knowledge categories, using multidimensional criteria, namely accuracy, response time, and content comprehensiveness.¹⁹ In the existing literature, most studies tend to focus on a single model or utilize a limited number of evaluation parameters; thus, comprehensive and multivariate analyses such as the present one remain relatively scarce.³¹ Moreover, the assessment of each model not only in terms of overall performance but also across individual subcategories of knowledge provides a significant advantage in evaluating their suitability for both clinical and educational contexts.²⁸

Nevertheless, this study has certain limitations. First, all questions were presented exclusively in Turkish, which may have adversely affected the performance of models with limited Turkish language support.³⁵ This highlights the variability in language-based response quality among LLMs.³² In addition, the use of a limited number of multiple-choice questions per category may have restricted the depth of analysis in certain knowledge domains.^{14,29,36} Moreover, although some of the evaluated models support multimodal inputs, the present assessment was restricted to text-only multiple-choice questions and did not incorporate image-based dental queries, such as radiographs, intraoral photographs, or clinical images.³⁷⁻³⁹ As visual data play a central role in real-world dental diagnosis and treatment planning, this represents an important limitation and a recognized gap of text-only benchmarking approaches. Consequently, the findings should not be generalized to multimodal clinical scenarios involving image interpretation.

Given the continuously evolving nature of LLMs, the results obtained are specific to the particular model versions used at the time of data collection.³³ Furthermore, as the study is based on theoretical knowledge, the generalizability of its findings to real-world clinical applications may be limited.³⁷⁻³⁹ Lastly, the ChatGPT-o3-mini model, which demonstrated the highest accuracy in our evaluation, is no longer available as a public-facing model. Consequently, reproducibility of these results using current versions (e.g., o4-mini or standard o3) may vary. Another limitation is that explicit user-selectable inference run modes (such as deep reasoning versus fast or low-latency modes) were not available via the public web interfaces of the evaluated models during the study period. As a result, all models were assessed under their default platform-defined execution settings, and potential performance differences attributable to alternative run modes could not be examined.^{36,40} Despite these limitations, the present study objectively delineates the strengths and weaknesses of current LLMs in text-based dental knowledge assessment, thereby offering a meaningful contribution to the literature, particularly in the context of dental education and clinical decision-support systems.

This study highlights the performance differences of LLMs across dentistry-specific knowledge domains and provides valuable insights into their potential for clinical and educational use. In particular, the superior balance of accuracy and content demonstrated by ChatGPT-based models suggests their suitability for educational applications and clinical decision support. Future studies incorporating broader datasets, multilingual input, and case-based scenarios will be essential to further validate and deepen these findings, ultimately supporting the effective integration of LLM into dental practice.

5. Conclusion

This study compared the performance of five distinct LLMs across dentistry-specific knowledge domains, revealing that each model exhibits unique strengths. While ChatGPT-o3-mini stood out in terms of accuracy, Microsoft Copilot excelled in response speed, and Google Gemini 2.0 Flash delivered the most comprehensive content. The findings clearly indicate that the selection of an LLMs should be based on the intended purpose of use. In an era of rapidly advancing AI technologies, such multidimensional and comparative analyses serve as valuable guidance for both clinical and educational applications.

References

- Arjumand B. The application of artificial intelligence in restorative dentistry: A narrative review of current research. *Saudi Dent J*. 2024.
- de Magalhães AA, Santos AT. Advancements in diagnostic methods and imaging technologies in dentistry: A literature review of emerging approaches. *J Clin Med*. 2025;14(4):1277.
- Batra AM, Reche A. A new era of dental care: Harnessing artificial intelligence for better diagnosis and treatment. *Cureus*. 2023;15(11).
- Abdulakhatov J, Oxunov B. A review of advancements of artificial intelligence in dentistry. *Web Med J Med Pract Nurs*. 2025;3(3):118–142.
- Dhopte A, Bagde H. Smart smile: Revolutionizing dentistry with artificial intelligence. *Cureus*. 2023;15(6).
- Ghods K, Azizi A, Jafari A, Ghods K. Application of artificial intelligence in clinical dentistry: A comprehensive review of literature. *J Dent*. 2023;24(4):356.
- Carrillo-Perez F, Pecho OE, Morales JC, Paravina RD, Della Bona A, Ghinea R, et al. Applications of artificial intelligence in dentistry: A comprehensive review. *J Esthet Restor Dent*. 2022;34(1):259–280.
- Shan T, Tay FR, Gu L. Application of artificial intelligence in dentistry. *J Dent Res*. 2021;100(3):232–244.
- Revilla-León M, Gómez-Polo M, Vyas S, Barmak AB, Özcan M, Att W, et al. Artificial intelligence applications in restorative dentistry: A systematic review. *J Prosthet Dent*. 2022;128(5):867–875.
- Shafi I, Fatima A, Afzal H, Díez I del T, Lipari V, Breñosa J, et al. A comprehensive review of recent advances in artificial intelligence for dentistry e-health. *Diagnostics*. 2023;13(13):2196.
- Semerci ZM, Yardımcı S. Empowering modern dentistry: The impact of artificial intelligence on patient care and clinical decision making. *Diagnostics*. 2024;14(12):1260.
- Dutta A, Pasricha N, Singh RK, Revanna R, Ramanna PK. Harnessing artificial intelligence in dentistry: Enhancing patient care and diagnostic precision. *J Dent Sci*. 2024.
- Moeini A, Torabi S. The role of artificial intelligence in dental diagnosis and treatment planning. *J Oral Dent Health Nexus*. 2025;2(1):14–26.
- Nguyen HC, Dang HP, Nguyen TL, Hoang V, Nguyen VA. Accuracy of latest large language models in answering multiple-choice questions in dentistry: A comparative study. *PLoS One*. 2025;20(1):e0317423.
- Landis JR, Koch GG. The measurement of observer agreement for categorical data. *Biometrics*. 1977;33:159–174.
- Akoglu H. User's guide to correlation coefficients. *Turk J Emerg Med*. 2018;18(3):91–93.
- Yılmaz BE, Gokkurt Yılmaz BN, Ozbey F. Artificial intelligence performance in answering multiple-choice oral pathology questions: A comparative analysis. *BMC Oral Health*. 2025;25(1):573.
- Sallam M, Al-Adwan AS, Mijwil MM, Abdelaziz DH, Al-Qaisi A, Ibrahim OM, et al. Technology readiness, social influence, and anxiety as predictors of university educators' perceptions of generative AI usefulness and effectiveness. *Front Artif Intell*. 2025;8:1571527.
- Reyhan AH, Mutaf Ç, Uzun İ, Yüksekayla F. A performance evaluation of large language models in keratoconus. *J Clin Med*. 2024;13(21):6512.
- Llorente de Pedro M, Suárez A, Algar J, Díaz-Flores García V, Andreu-Vázquez C, Freire Y. Assessing ChatGPT's reliability in endodontics. *Appl Sci*. 2025;15(10):5231.
- Batool H, Mukhtar A, Khawaja SG, et al. Knowledge distillation and transformer-based framework for automatic spine CT report generation. *IEEE Access*. 2025; ahead of print.
- Xu J, Wang Y. Enhancing healthcare recommendation systems with multimodal LLMs-based MOE architecture. Paper presented at: 5th International Conference on Signal Processing and Machine Learning; 2025.
- Naqvi WM, Ganjoo R, Rowe M, et al. Critical thinking in the age of generative AI. *Front Artif Intell*. 2024;8:1571527.
- Hatia A, Doldo T, Parrini S, et al. Accuracy and completeness of ChatGPT-generated information on interceptive orthodontics. *J Clin Med*. 2024;13(3):735.
- Sallam M, Alasfoor IM, Khalid SW, et al. Chinese generative AI models rival ChatGPT-4 in ophthalmology queries. *Narra J*. 2025;5(1):e2371.
- Maes SH. The circle of life for LLMs. 2025; ahead of print.
- Neha F, Bhati D. A survey of DeepSeek models. Authorea Preprints. 2025.
- Gao T, Jin J, Ke ZT, Moryoussef G. A comparison of DeepSeek and other LLMs. *arXiv preprint*. 2025;arXiv:250203688.
- Joshi S. A comprehensive review of DeepSeek. 2025; ahead of print.
- Jelodar H, Meymani M, Razavi-Far R. Large language models for source code analysis. *arXiv preprint*. 2025;arXiv:250317502.
- Rahman A, Mahir SH, Tashrif MTA, et al. Comparative analysis of DeepSeek, ChatGPT, and Gemini. *arXiv preprint*. 2025;arXiv:250304783.
- Ong QC, Ang CS, Chee DZY, et al. Advancing health coaching with LLMs. *Artif Intell Med*. 2024;157:103004.
- Agha AS. Evaluating AI efficiency in backend software development. 2025; ahead of print.
- Lafourcade C, Kérourédan O, Ballester B, Richert R. Accuracy and contextual understanding of LLMs in dentistry. *J Dent*. 2025;157:105764.
- Moreno-Molina M, Suresh A, Colman RE, Rodwell TC. Facilitating user interaction with the tuberculosis mutation catalogue using AI tools. *bioRxiv*. 2025.
- Nguyen VA, Ha TBN, Tran MN, et al. Speed–accuracy trade-off of LLMs on oral surgery MCQs. *Sci Rep*. 2025;15(1):40657.
- Carboni L. Code generation on a diet. 2024; ahead of print.
- Nguyen VA, Vuong TQT, Nguyen VH. Benchmarking LLM vision in oral anatomy. *PLoS One*. 2025;20(10):e0335775.
- Nguyen VA, Nguyen VH, Vuong TQT, Truong QT, Nguyen TT. Comparative reasoning in oral pathology diagnosis. *PLoS One*. 2025;20(12):e0340220.
- Nguyen VA, Vuong TQT, Nguyen V. Comparative performance of deep-reasoning and lightweight LLMs on oral implantology MCQs. *Int J Prosthodont*. 2025;38:1–20.

AI Declaration

Chatgpt 4o was used for language editing to improve grammar and clarity. All data collection, screening, analysis, visualization, and interpretation were performed manually and independently verified by the author.

Conflict of Interest

All authors declare no conflicts of interest.

CRedit Author Statement

M. B. : Methodology, Investigation, Data curation
F.P.H. : Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration

Data Availability Statement

Data available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Ethics Approval

Not applicable.

Funding

No external funding.

How to cite this article:

Baytar M, Pertek Hatipoğlu F. Performance Comparison of Large Language Models in Dentistry: A Focus on Restorative Dentistry Using Turkish Specialty Exam Questions. *J Endod Restor Dent.* 2026; 4(1):7-14.
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.18585386

Review Article

Postoperative Tooth Sensitivity in Direct Resin Composite Restorations: Etiology, Diagnosis, and Management

Danuchit Banomyong ^a

^a Faculty of Dentistry, Mahidol University, Bangkok, Thailand

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 26.11.2025
Completion of First Review: 21.12.2025
Accepted: 31.12.2025
Published: 01.03.2026

KEYWORDS

Dental Adhesive
Direct Restoration
Postoperative Tooth Sensitivity
Resin composite

CORRESPONDENCE

Danuchit Banomyong
Faculty of Dentistry, Mahidol University,
Bangkok, Thailand
E-mail: danuchitb@gmail.com

CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

PTS could be prevented by correct diagnosis, minimal-trauma operative procedures, proper adhesive application under good moisture control, appropriate resin composite material, oblique incremental placement, and careful occlusion check.

ABSTRACT

Postoperative tooth sensitivity (PTS) is a complication associated with direct resin composite restorations, presenting as a short, sharp pain in response to stimuli. The possible mechanism is the hydrodynamic theory, which proposes that restoration defects, such as micro-gaps between the restoration and dentin, induce dentinal fluid movement that triggers pulpal nerve fibers. The incidence of PTS in direct restorations ranges from 0 to 25%. The risk of PTS has a direct relationship with cavity depth and size. Clinical evidence demonstrates no significant difference in PTS between etch-and-rinse and self-etching adhesive systems. The use of glass-ionomer cement or flowable composite liner may not reduce PTS. Errors in bonding procedures potentially lead to PTS. PTS may arise from three possible etiologies: I. transient pulpal inflammation (from preoperative insults or operative trauma); II. incomplete sealing of exposed dentine (marginal or internal gaps); and III. tooth and restoration deformation from occlusal force. Prevention strategies include minimizing operative trauma, strictly following adhesive instructions with contamination control, ensuring appropriate thickness of resin composite, incremental restoring for adaptation to cavity walls, and checking occlusion. Management strategies involve monitoring, desensitizer application, re-bonding to seal gaps or exposed dentine, repairing the defects, or replacement.

1. Introduction

Postoperative tooth sensitivity (PTS) is frequently reported as a complication following direct resin composite restorations. PTS is defined as a short, sharp pain (hypersensitivity) in response to one or more stimuli, including cold/hot water, sweet substances, occlusal force, or tooth brushing.¹ Understanding the etiology and contributing clinical factors is crucial for effective prevention and management. The objective of this review article is to describe the mechanism, clinical factors, etiology, prevention, diagnosis, and management of PTS.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Mechanism of postoperative tooth sensitivity

Dentine sensitivity is primarily explained by the hydrodynamic theory, which proposes that stimuli induce movement of the dentinal fluid, subsequently triggering pulpal nerve fibers and causing sensitivity.² In the context of PTS, defects such as micro-gaps between the restoration and the dentin allow fluid movement, leading to sensitivity after restorations.

2.2. Incidence and clinical factors

The incidence of PTS varies based on the restoration cavity, ranging from 0–25% in Class I and II restorations, typically at a low to moderate level.^{3–8} The incidence in Class II restorations is generally higher than in Class I. In some cases, PTS may decrease over time and self-relieved within 30 days.^{4,5,7} Even clinical studies report incidences of PTS in Class V restorations as usually less than 5%^{9,10}, the practical incidence is likely to be higher. The incidences in class III and IV restorations are usually rare^{11,12}. Clinical factors

that may relate to the risk of PTS are discussed as follows (Table 1):

Cavity characteristics: Cavity type, depth, and size are important factors. For cavity type, as previously mentioned, PTS is most commonly reported in Class I, II, and V restorations.¹¹ For cavity depth, the risk of PTS has a direct relationship with the depth. When the residual dentine thickness corresponds to the inner one-third of the dentine, the risk of PTS is four times greater.⁸ If pulp exposure, the risk of PTS is 14 times higher.³ For cavity size, the incidence of PTS increases with the size of the cavity (e.g., MOD cavity > OM/OD cavity > O cavity).⁴

Sclerotic dentine: Sclerotic dentine is characterized by lower permeability compared to normal dentine.¹³ While bonding to sclerotic dentine is less effective than to normal dentine, preserving it keeps the dentinal tubules occluded, which, according to the hydrodynamic theory, makes PTS less likely after restorations.

Adhesive mode: The comparison between etch-and-rinse (ER) and self-etching (SE) adhesives regarding PTS incidence has been thoroughly studied. Although concerns exist regarding the technique sensitivity of ER and whether SE provides a better "seal"^{14,15}, clinical evidence reveals no significant difference in the incidence or intensity of PTS between the two adhesive modes in Class I, Class II, or Class V restorations.^{5,16–19} In vitro, ER adhesives have demonstrated a comparable dentine seal to SE adhesives in fluid flow and micro-permeability tests.^{13,15} From a systematic review and meta-analysis, PTS in class I and II restorations are not different between the two adhesives, regardless of cavity types.^{20,21} For universal adhesives, the use of the SE mode resulted in lower

Table 1. Clinical factors that may associate with PTS after resin composite restoration (PTS: postoperative tooth sensitivity).

Clinical factors associated with PTS	Incidence of PTS
Cavity characteristics	Cavity type: Class II, I, and V Cavity depth: Inner 1/3 of dentine, or pulpal exposure. Cavity size: Class II MOD > Class II MO/OD.
Presence of sclerotic dentine	Absence > Presence
Adhesive mode and restorative technique	No difference between etch-and-rinse (ER) and self-etching (SE) adhesives. Universal adhesive: SE mode < ER mode (a low incidence of PTS). No difference between bulk-fill and traditional resin composite (bulk-fill vs. incremental placement).
Cavity lining	Lining with glass-ionomer cement or flowable resin composite does not decrease incidence of PTS.
Preoperative tooth sensitivity	Not increase risk of PTS.

Fig. 1. Three primary types of PTS have been proposed: [1] Type I: temporary pulpal inflammation; [2] Type II: incomplete sealing of exposed dentine; and [3] Type III: tooth and restoration deformation.

PTS compared to the ER mode.²² However, the incidence of PTS of universal adhesive is low and not different from that of conventional ER or SE adhesive.²³ For restorative materials, no difference in PTS between bulk-fill and traditional resin composite has been reported in a systematic review and meta-analysis.²⁴ However, incremental placement of restoration to ensure adaptation to cavity and effective light-curing would be beneficial.

Presence of Lining: The use of glass-ionomer cement (GIC) or flowable composite lining has traditionally been recommended to prevent PTS.^{11,25} GIC has been theorized to offer an effective seal via chemical bond, biocompatibility, and stress absorption.²⁶ However, clinical evidence indicates that GIC lining is unlikely to reduce PTS, irrespective of whether ER or SE adhesives are used.^{5,27,28} In addition, internal gap formation tends to be higher when GIC lining is applied in a very thin layer (e.g., 0.5 mm thick) compared to a thicker layer (e.g., 1 mm thick).

Flowable composite lining may improve adaptation due to its flow capacity and act as a stress absorption layer, but laboratory studies show insignificant results between the absence or presence of a flowable composite layer.^{29,30} Clinically, PTS in class V restorations are not different between with or without a flowable composite liner.²⁵

Preoperative tooth sensitivity: The presence of preoperative sensitivity may not be related to the occurrence of PTS. Many patients who exhibited PTS after restorations do not report any

preoperative symptoms.^{5,31} Conversely, the teeth with symptomatic reversible pulpitis are usually relieved after removing the causes (such as dental caries) and restoring with resin composite, which do not show any PTS.^{31,32}

2.3. Etiology and prevention strategies of PTS

From laboratory and clinical studies, three primary etiologies of PTS have been proposed³³ (Fig. 1): I. temporary pulpal inflammation, resulting from previous injuries or operative procedures; II. incomplete sealing of exposed dentine, adjacent to restorations, marginal or internal gaps; and III. tooth and restoration deformation (TRD), induced by occlusal forces.

2.3.1. PTS Type I: Temporary pulpal inflammation

Temporary pulpal inflammation may arise from preoperative threads such as caries or cracks, which decrease the pain threshold of pulpal nerves.^{34,35} Moreover, operative trauma, including heat from insufficient coolant during preparation or polishing, vigorous air blasts causing odontoblast displacement, or heat generated during light curing in deep cavities, contributes to pulpal inflammation. The temporary inflammation of pulpal tissues may induce short-term PTS.¹⁸ However, when the cavity is appropriately sealed by restorations, the pulp usually exhibits self-recovery from minor operative injuries, and PTS is likely to diminish within 30-90 days.³⁻⁵

Fig. 2. Diagnosis and management of three primary types of PTS (color labeling: green- Type I, orange- Type II, and red- Type III).

Table 2: Methods used for assessment, differential diagnosis, and follow-up duration of PTS after resin composite restoration (PTS: postoperative tooth sensitivity).

Clinical symptoms of PTS	Assessment methods for PTS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sensitive to occlusal force Sensitive to cold water, sweet, brushing, or others 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Checking high-spot occlusion using articulating paper. Testing with biting or pressing force (e.g. biting on object or tooth slooth; and pressing with ball burnisher or plugger). Examining quality/any defects of restorations and adjacent exposed dentine. Radiographic examination: bitewing and/or periapical radiograph to reveal inadequate thickness of restoration or any internal gap. Try to trigger the PTS by using the stimulus reported by patients. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Cold water test under rubber dam isolation (one by one). -Sugary syrup. -Tactile force e.g. exploration. To identify the tooth and the area of PTS. Examining quality/any defects of restorations, and nearby exposed dentine. Radiographic examination: bitewing and/or periapical radiograph to reveal any marginal gap, particularly at gingival margins.
Differential diagnosis:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cracked tooth: history of crack, exploration of crack after restoration removal. Pulp pathosis: history of pulpal exposure, signs and symptoms of irreversible pulpitis, re-evaluation of pulpal and periapical status. Refer pain: other odontogenic or non-odontogenic origin. 	
Follow-up duration:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PTS from operative injuries (PTS type I) without any defects of restorations should be subsided in 30 days. Teeth with PTS last longer than 30 days should be carefully re-evaluated to identify definite cause(s). If any defects are detected (PTS type II or III), the defective restorations should be sealed, repaired, or replaced immediately. 	

Prevention for Type I PTS requires minimal-trauma operative techniques, including ensuring adequate air-water coolant during cavity preparation, using a short-duration air blast, and utilizing low light-curing intensity for the adhesive layer in deep cavities.³³

2.3.2. PTS Type II: Incomplete seal of dentine (dentine exposed, marginal, or internal gaps)

Incomplete seals of restorations lead to gaps that provide a pathway for dentinal fluid movement, inducing the sensitivity.^{13,15} Gaps can be marginal (extending from enamel into dentine) or internal (at the bonded dentin interface). Marginal gap formation is more likely at sub-gingival dentine margins in Class II and V restorations due to less reliable dentine adhesion.^{36,37} Micro-gaps are formed by polymerization shrinkage, incorrect use of the

dentine bonding agent (e.g., prolonged etching, excessive drying, or inappropriate application of primer/adhesive), or contamination (saliva, blood, or astringent) during bonding procedures.³⁸⁻⁴⁰ Most errors leading to PTS are probably from improper bonding procedures. Using an intermediate layer between dentine and resin composite, such as flowable liner or glass-ionomer lining cement, does not improve gap-free restorations^{15,37,41,42} or reduce PTS.^{6,27} In contrast, placement techniques of resin composite may affect the chances of internal and marginal gap formation. The incremental layering technique of resin composite tends to decrease internal/marginal gaps compared to the bulk filling technique, which may contain interfacial voids at the cavity walls.^{43,44} However, a clinical study reported that PTS after restorations with incremental and bulk placements are not significantly different.⁴⁵

Type II PTS may occur from remaining exposed dentine adjacent to cavity margins that is not included in the restoration.³³ This exposed dentine area may not be sensitive before restorations due to dentinal sclerosis and obstruction of dentinal tubules.⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸ However, it can become sensitive after restorations, possibly from over-acid-etching or aggressive polishing that can remove the superficial sclerotic layer and then expose the normal 'sensitive' dentine.^{49,50}

Prevention for Type II PTS centers on strictly following

Fig. 3. Representative clinical cases of postoperative tooth sensitivity (PTS) Types I and II.

(A–B) PTS Type I associated with preoperative insult and operative trauma.

(A) Deep dental caries in the maxillary right second premolar.

(B) Following resin composite restoration, the patient reported sensitivity to thermal change (cold), which gradually decreased and completely resolved within two weeks.

(C–D) PTS Type II associated with marginal gaps.

(C) A periapical radiograph showing a clearly detectable marginal gap at the gingival margin (red arrow) of a resin composite restoration on the mandibular left first molar, associated with persistent sensitivity to cold water for several weeks.

(D) A marginal gap at the distal margin of a cervical restoration (red arrow) highlighted after staining with a caries detector dye; chronic postoperative tooth sensitivity was reported following restoration.

Fig. 4. A case showing PTS Type II relating to the internal gap. (A) A radiographic image of the maxillary left second molar with mesio-occlusal resin composite restoration. A radiolucent area was observed under the restoration (red arrow). The patient reported PTS to occlusal function for months, and was also sensitive to loading force from a ball burnisher or plugger when pressing on the restoration surface above the internal gap area. (B) An internal gap was clearly detected (red arrow) after removal of the restoration. This internal gap was potentially due to a poor resin-composite condensing technique.

Fig. 5. A case showing PTS Type II relating to exposed dentine adjacent to the restoration. (A) On the maxillary right first molar, exposed dentine areas (red arrows) were found adjacent to the resin composite restoration. Without any preoperative symptoms, the patient reported PTS when chewing and drinking cold water. No 'red spots' from articulating paper were noticed on the restoration surface after occlusion checking. (B) Another exposed dentine was observed on the buccal side (white arrow) from a non-carious cervical lesion near the proximal margin of the restoration. Both exposed dentine areas were sensitive to cold-water testing and tactile testing. (C) At two-week recall after restoration replacement and cervical restoration, the patient reported that the restored tooth was normal and not sensitive to the stimuli.

manufacturer instructions for dental adhesives, maintaining adequate moisture control (e.g., rubber dam isolation), ensuring any contamination control, and utilizing proper placement techniques for resin composite.³³ Furthermore, exposed dentine adjacent to cavity margins should be sealed in the adhesive procedure, particularly when acid etching is used, or included in the outline of restorations. In addition, polishing of restorations should be carefully performed to prevent iatrogenic damage of adjacent dentine surfaces.³³

2.3.3. PTS Type III: Tooth/restoration deformation (TRD)

TRD might occur when occlusal forces induce mechanical

Fig. 6. A case showing PTS Type III relating to TRD due to inadequate thickness of restoration. (A) After occluso-proximal resin composite restoration on the mandibular left second molar, the patient complained about PTS when biting force close to the center of the restoration (red arrow). The restored tooth was also sensitive to the loading force when using a ball burnisher or plunger pressing on the suspected area. (B) A thin layer of resin composite at the sensitivity area was revealed in a periapical radiograph (red arrow) and after removal of restoration, which was less than 1 mm thick. After replacement, PTS disappeared by an increase in cavity depth and, subsequently, the thickness of the replaced resin composite restoration.

deformation of the enamel/dentin, leading to cuspal deflection and dentinal fluid movement.^{51,52} TRD is possible in large Class I and II cavities, particularly when the resin composite lacks sufficient modulus of elasticity or thickness.⁵³⁻⁵⁵ The larger the cavity (MOD), the higher the incidence of PTS probably due to increased TRD and cuspal tension from polymerization shrinkage stress.^{4,56,57} A minimum thickness of 1–1.5 mm of resin composite, theoretically with 60% filler loading by volume, should be used for posterior restorations to reduce deformation and resultant stress.^{53,54} Moreover, 'oblique' incremental placement of resin composite lowers shrinkage stress and cuspal deflection, by decreasing the volume of material in each layer and cavity configuration factor, compared to the bulk placement.^{58,59} However, 'horizontal' incremental placement should be avoided due to higher shrinkage stress detected.^{58,59} Traumatic occlusion or para-functional habits tends to increase the risk of TRD.^{33,60}

Prevention for Type III PTS involves proper case selection, particularly in large restorations^{61,62}, use of resin composite with appropriate elastic modulus and thickness, maintaining minimal cavity size, oblique incremental placement technique, and meticulously checking occlusion.³³

2.4. Diagnosis and management of PTS

PTS would be a symptom of reversible pulpitis to any stimuli that should be differentially diagnosed from other conditions after restorations, such as cracked teeth with persistent symptoms or restored teeth developing irreversible pulpitis.⁶³⁻⁶⁶ Diagnosis and management of three types of PTS have been proposed (Fig. 2). The diagnosis and management should rely on identifying the specific stimuli and causes inducing the sensitivity. Methods used for assessment, differential diagnosis, and follow-up duration of PTS are described in Table 2.

2.4.1. PTS Type I

PTS resulting from reversible pulpitis (Type I) due to operative trauma is present usually when thermal stimuli induce sensitivity, but none of the exposed dentine, gaps, or traumatic occlusion is detected³³ (Fig. 3A-3B). Importantly, this PTS in non-cracked teeth tends to resolve spontaneously within 30 days after proper restorations.³

Management of PTS Type I includes informing the patient and, probably, using self-applied desensitizers that interact with neural transmission (e.g., containing potassium nitrate). However, cracked teeth with preoperative sensitivity have a high incidence of prolonged PTS after restoration with resin composite, with a few teeth later showing signs of pulpal pathology.⁶⁴ Thus, the PTS in the restored, cracked teeth should be carefully interpreted and monitored.

2.4.2. PTS Type II

PTS relating to incomplete seals of dentine (Type II) could be induced by thermal, tactile exploration, or occlusal force.³³ Marginal gaps may be visually or radiographically detected and, if extending to dentine, potentially induce sensitivity to thermal changes⁶⁷ (Fig. 3C-3D). In contrast, internal gaps are more difficult to detect (Fig. 4). However, loading tactile force or pressing on the suspected area of internal gaps may induce sensitivity due to stimulation of dentinal fluid movement inside the internal gaps.^{15,51} For the sensitivity from exposed dentine adjacent to the restorative margins, the area of sensitive dentine can be confirmed by visualization and tactile exploration.^{68,69} (Fig. 5).

Management options of PTS Type II include re-bonding to seal marginal gaps or exposed dentine, repairing the defective margins, or covering the adjacent sensitive dentine with restorations.³³ Replacement of restorations may be necessary, particularly in the internal gaps.³³ In addition, for exposed sensitive dentine adjacent to the restorative margins, professional or self-applied desensitizers (e.g., containing fluoride, glutaraldehyde,

oxalate, or bioactive glass) may be used in an attempt to occlude the dentinal tubules.⁷⁰⁻⁷²

2.4.3. PTS Type III

PTS due to TRD (Type III) is potentially sensitive to occlusal force.³³ Occlusion should first be rechecked to identify any traumatic 'high-spot' on restorations. For the non-traumatic causes, PTS to occlusal force might relate to material deficiencies (too thin or non-rigid composite), inducing cuspal deflection.^{53,54,60,73} The inadequate thickness of restorations may be detected from bitewing radiographs or after initial removal of restorations (Fig. 6). However, PTS type III should be carefully distinguished from PTS Type II, in particular the internal gaps, which both are likely to be induced by occlusal function.

For management of PTS Type III, occlusal adjustment of restorations should be firstly performed if traumatic occlusion on restorations is detected. In the non-traumatic cases, replacement of restorations should be considered, to utilize a more rigid resin composite or increase restoration thickness.³³

3. Conclusion

PTS following direct resin composite restorations is a complication defined as a short, sharp pain in response to stimuli. The risk of PTS has a direct relationship with cavity depth and size. For adhesive type, clinical evidence demonstrates no significant difference in PTS among etch-and-rinse, self-etching, and universal adhesives. The use of cavity liner/base may not reduce PTS. PTS possibly arises from three proposed etiologies: (I) pulpal inflammation due to preoperative injuries or operative trauma; (II) incomplete sealing of exposed dentinal tubules, leading to marginal or inside gaps; and (III) tooth and restoration deformation caused by occlusal forces.

Prevention of PTS is based on minimal-trauma operative techniques (Type I PTS); strict adherence to bonding protocols, contamination control, and proper restorative technique (Type II PTS); and careful occlusion checking, proper material selection, and thickness (Type III PTS). Management strategies range from monitoring by informing possibility of self-relieving in short-term PTS (especially deep cavities) to operating management, including traumatic occlusion adjustment, applying desensitizing agents, re-bonding to seal gaps or exposed dentine, repairing the marginal defects, or, ultimately, replacement of the restorations.

References

- Dababneh RH, Khouri AT, Addy M. Dentine hypersensitivity - an enigma? A review of terminology, mechanisms, aetiology and management. *Br Dent J*. 1999;187(11):606-611; discussion 603.
- Brannstrom M. The hydrodynamic theory of dentinal pain: sensation in preparations, caries, and the dentinal crack syndrome. *J Endod*. 1986;12(10):453-457.
- Auschill TM, Koch CA, Wolkewitz M, Hellwig E, Arweiler NB. Occurrence and causing stimuli of postoperative sensitivity in composite restorations. *Oper Dent*. 2009;34(1):3-10.
- Briso AL, Mestreneur SR, Delicio G, Sundfeld RH, Bedran-Russo AK, de Alexandre RS, et al. Clinical assessment of postoperative sensitivity in posterior composite restorations. *Oper Dent*. 2007;32(5):421-426.
- Burrow MF, Banomyong D, Harnirattisai C, Messer HH. Effect of glass-ionomer cement lining on postoperative sensitivity in occlusal cavities restored with resin composite--a randomized clinical trial. *Oper Dent*. 2009;34(6):648-655.
- Perdigão J, Anauate-Netto C, Carmo AR, Hodges JS, Cordeiro HJ, Lewgoy HR, et al. The effect of adhesive and flowable composite on postoperative sensitivity: 2-week results. *Quintessence Int*. 2004;35(10):777-784.
- Swift EJ, Jr., Ritter AV, Heymann HO, Sturdevant JR, Wilder AD, Jr. 36-month clinical evaluation of two adhesives and microhybrid resin composites in Class I restorations. *Am J Dent*. 2008;21(3):148-152.
- Unemori M, Matsuya Y, Akashi A, Goto Y, Akamine A. Composite resin restoration and postoperative sensitivity: clinical follow-up in an undergraduate program. *J Dent*. 2001;29(1):7-13.
- Pollington S, van Noort R. A clinical evaluation of a resin composite and a compomer in non-cariou Class V lesions. A 3-year follow-up. *Am J Dent*. 2008;21(1):49-52.
- Türkün LS, Celik EU. Noncarious class V lesions restored with a polyacid modified resin composite and a nanocomposite: a two-year clinical trial. *J Adhes Dent*. 2008;10(5):399-405.
- Christensen GJ. Preventing postoperative tooth sensitivity in class I, II and V restorations. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 2002;133(2):229-231.
- van Dijken JW. Durability of new restorative materials in Class III cavities. *J Adhes Dent*. 2001;3(1):65-70.
- Banomyong D, Palamara JE, Messer HH, Burrow MF. Fluid flow after resin-composite restoration in extracted carious teeth. *Eur J Oral Sci*. 2009;117(3):334-342.
- Banomyong D, Palamara JE, Burrow MF, Messer HH. Effect of dentin conditioning on dentin permeability and micro-shear bond strength. *Eur J Oral Sci*. 2007;115(6):502-509.
- Banomyong D, Palamara JE, Messer HH, Burrow MF. Sealing ability of occlusal resin composite restoration using four restorative procedures. *Eur J Oral Sci*. 2008;116(6):571-578.
- Browning WD, Blalock JS, Callan RS, Brackett WW, Schull GF, Davenport MB, et al. Postoperative sensitivity: a comparison of two bonding agents. *Oper Dent*. 2007;32(2):112-117.
- Perdigão J, Geraldini S, Hodges JS. Total-etch versus self-etch adhesive: effect on postoperative sensitivity. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 2003;134(12):1621-1629.
- Blanchard P, Wong Y, Matthews AG, Vena D, Craig RG, Curro FA, et al. Restoration variables and postoperative hypersensitivity in Class I restorations: PEARL Network findings. Part 2. *Compend Contin Educ Dent*. 2013;34(4):e62-68.
- Fang K, Chen K, Shi M, Wang L. Effect of different adhesive systems on dental defects and sensitivity to teeth in composite resin restoration: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clin Oral Investig*. 2023;27(6):2495-2511.
- Reis A, Dourado Loguercio A, Schroeder M, Luque-Martinez I, Masterson D, Cople Maia L. Does the adhesive strategy influence the post-operative sensitivity in adult patients with posterior resin composite restorations?: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Dent Mater*. 2015;31(9):1052-1067.
- Schroeder M, Correa IC, Bauer J, Loguercio AD, Reis A. Influence of adhesive strategy on clinical parameters in cervical restorations: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Dent*. 2017;62:36-53.
- Assis P, Silva C, Nascimento A, Annibal H, Júnior S, Soares N, et al. Does Acid Etching Influence the Adhesion of Universal Adhesive Systems in Noncarious Cervical Lesions? A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Oper Dent*. 2023;48(4):373-390.
- Polesso Patias M, Fernandes ESP, Carreño NLV, Lund RG, Piva E, da Silva AF, et al. Comparative clinical performance of universal adhesives versus etch-and-rinse and self-etch adhesives: a meta-analysis. *Clin Oral Investig*. 2025;29(7):352.
- Kunz PVM, Wambier LM, Kaizer MDR, Correr GM, Reis A, Gonzaga CC. Is the clinical performance of composite resin restorations in posterior teeth similar if restored with incremental or bulk-filling techniques? A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Clin Oral Investig*. 2022;26(3):2281-2297.

25. Miguez PA, Pereira PN, Foxton RM, Walter R, Nunes MF, Swift EJ, Jr. Effects of flowable resin on bond strength and gap formation in Class I restorations. *Dent Mater.* 2004;20(9):839-845.
26. Rath DN, Palamara JE, Messer HH. Minimizing dentinal fluid flow associated with gap formation. *J Dent Res.* 2006;85(11):1027-1031.
27. Strober B, Veitz-Keenan A, Barna JA, Matthews AG, Vena D, Craig RG, et al. Effectiveness of a resin-modified glass ionomer liner in reducing hypersensitivity in posterior restorations: a study from the practitioners engaged in applied research and learning network. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 2013;144(8):886-897.
28. Unemori M, Matsuya Y, Hyakutake H, Matsuya S, Goto Y, Akamine A. Long-term follow-up of composite resin restorations with self-etching adhesives. *J Dent.* 2007;35(6):535-540.
29. Ausiello PP, Ciaramella S, Lanzotti A, Ventre M, Borges AL, Tribst JP, et al. Mechanical behavior of Class I cavities restored by different material combinations under loading and polymerization shrinkage stress. A 3D-FEA study. *Am J Dent.* 2019;32(2):55-60.
30. Pongprueksa P, Kuphasuk W, Senawongse P. Effect of elastic cavity wall and occlusal loading on microleakage and dentin bond strength. *Oper Dent.* 2007;32(5):466-475.
31. Berkowitz G, Spielman H, Matthews A, Vena D, Craig R, Curro F, et al. Postoperative hypersensitivity and its relationship to preparation variables in Class I resin-based composite restorations: findings from the practitioners engaged in applied research and learning (PEARL) Network. Part 1. *Compend Contin Educ Dent.* 2013;34(3):e44-52.
32. Kayaci Ş T, Yazici ZS, Kinikoğlu İ, Özüdoğru S, Arslan H. A randomized controlled clinical trial of the performance of three bioactive endodontic cements in primary molar teeth diagnosed with reversible pulpitis: 1-year follow-up study. *J Dent.* 2024;150:105378.
33. Banomyong D. Postoperative tooth hypersensitivity associated with direct resin composite restorations. *J Thai Oper Dent.* 2011;10(2):27-43.
34. Rodd HD, Boissonade FM. Substance P expression in human tooth pulp in relation to caries and pain experience. *Eur J Oral Sci.* 2000;108(6):467-474.
35. Rodd HD, Boissonade FM. Innervation of human tooth pulp in relation to caries and dentition type. *J Dent Res.* 2001;80(1):389-393.
36. Correia AMO, Pereira VEM, Bresciani E, Platt JA, Borges ALS, Caneppele TMF. Influence of cavosurface angle on the stress concentration and gaps formation in class V resin composite restorations. *J Mech Behav Biomed Mater.* 2019;97:272-277.
37. Lindberg A, van Dijken JW, Hörstedt P. In vivo interfacial adaptation of class II resin composite restorations with and without a flowable resin composite liner. *Clin Oral Investig.* 2005;9(2):77-83.
38. Frankenberger R, Krämer N, Petschelt A. Technique sensitivity of dentin bonding: effect of application mistakes on bond strength and marginal adaptation. *Oper Dent.* 2000;25(4):324-330.
39. Hashimoto M, Tay FR, Svizero NR, de Gee AJ, Feilzer AJ, Sano H, et al. The effects of common errors on sealing ability of total-etch adhesives. *Dent Mater.* 2006;22(6):560-568.
40. Kuphasuk W, Harnirattisai C, Senawongse P, Tagami J. Bond strengths of two adhesive systems to dentin contaminated with a hemostatic agent. *Oper Dent.* 2007;32(4):399-405.
41. Nguyen AD, Bitter K, Gernhardt CR. Class-I and Class-II Restorations with the Application of a Flowable Composite as an Intermediate Layer-A Narrative Review of Clinical Trials. *J Funct Biomater.* 2025;16(3).
42. Chailert O, Banomyong D, Vongphan N, Ekworapoj P, Burrow MF. Internal adaptation of resin composite restorations with different thicknesses of glass ionomer cement lining. *J Investig Clin Dent.* 2018;9(2):e12308.
43. Alqudahai FS, Cook NB, Diefenderfer KE, Bottino MC, Platt JA. Comparison of Internal Adaptation of Bulk-fill and Increment-fill Resin Composite Materials. *Oper Dent.* 2019;44(1):E32-e44.
44. Kantovitz KR, Cabral LL, Carlos NR, de Freitas AZ, Peruzzo DC, Franca F, et al. Impact of Resin Composite Viscosity and Fill-technique on Internal Gap in Class I Restorations: An OCT Evaluation. *Oper Dent.* 2021;46(5):537-546.
45. Costa T, Rezende M, Sakamoto A, Bittencourt B, Dalzochio P, Loguercio AD, et al. Influence of Adhesive Type and Placement Technique on Postoperative Sensitivity in Posterior Composite Restorations. *Oper Dent.* 2017;42(2):143-154.
46. Senawongse P, Otsuki M, Tagami J, Mjör IA. Morphological characterization and permeability of attrited human dentine. *Arch Oral Biol.* 2008;53(1):14-19.
47. Vasiliadis L, Darling AI, Levers BG. The histology of sclerotic human root dentine. *Arch Oral Biol.* 1983;28(8):693-700.
48. Absi EG, Addy M, Adams D. Dentine hypersensitivity. A study of the patency of dentinal tubules in sensitive and non-sensitive cervical dentine. *J Clin Periodontol.* 1987;14(5):280-284.
49. Fogel HM, Pashley DH. Effect of periodontal root planing on dentin permeability. *J Clin Periodontol.* 1993;20(9):673-677.
50. Héritier M. Effects of phosphoric acid on root dentin surface. A scanning and transmission electron microscopic study. *J Periodontol Res.* 1984;19(2):168-176.
51. Paphangkorakit J, Osborn JW. The effect of normal occlusal forces on fluid movement through human dentine in vitro. *Arch Oral Biol.* 2000;45(12):1033-1041.
52. Rath DN, Palamara JE, Messer HH. Dentinal fluid flow and cuspal displacement in response to resin composite restorative procedures. *Dent Mater.* 2007;23(11):1405-1411.
53. Alster D, Feilzer AJ, de Gee AJ, Davidson CL. Polymerization contraction stress in thin resin composite layers as a function of layer thickness. *Dent Mater.* 1997;13(3):146-150.
54. El-Safty S, Silikas N, Watts DC. Creep deformation of restorative resin-composites intended for bulk-fill placement. *Dent Mater.* 2012;28(8):928-935.
55. Magne P, Oganessian T. CT scan-based finite element analysis of premolar cuspal deflection following operative procedures. *Int J Periodontics Restorative Dent.* 2009;29(4):361-369.
56. Panitvisai P, Messer HH. Cuspal deflection in molars in relation to endodontic and restorative procedures. *J Endod.* 1995;21(2):57-61.
57. Tantbirojn D, Versluis A, Pintado MR, DeLong R, Douglas WH. Tooth deformation patterns in molars after composite restoration. *Dent Mater.* 2004;20(6):535-542.
58. Oliveira AA, Ribeiro MLP, Costa PVM, Pereira RD, Versluis A, Veríssimo C. The effect of filling technique on the cuspal strain, polymerization shrinkage stress, enamel crack formation and depth of cure of restored molars. *Dent Mater.* 2022;38(8):1404-1418.
59. Soares CJ, Bicalho AA, Tantbirojn D, Versluis A. Polymerization shrinkage stresses in a premolar restored with different composite resins and different incremental techniques. *J Adhes Dent.* 2013;15(4):341-350.
60. Bicalho AA, Tantbirojn D, Versluis A, Soares CJ. Effect of occlusal loading and mechanical properties of resin composite on stress generated in posterior restorations. *Am J Dent.* 2014;27(3):129-133.

61. Deliperi S, Bardwell DN. Clinical evaluation of direct cuspal coverage with posterior composite resin restorations. *J Esthet Restor Dent*. 2006;18(5):256-265; discussion 266-257.
62. Fennis WM, Kuijs RH, Roeters FJ, Creugers NH, Kreulen CM. Randomized control trial of composite cuspal restorations: five-year results. *J Dent Res*. 2014;93(1):36-41.
63. Opdam NJ, Roeters JJ, Loomans BA, Bronkhorst EM. Seven-year clinical evaluation of painful cracked teeth restored with a direct composite restoration. *J Endod*. 2008;34(7):808-811.
64. Opdam NJ, Roeters JM. The effectiveness of bonded composite restorations in the treatment of painful, cracked teeth: six-month clinical evaluation. *Oper Dent*. 2003;28(4):327-333.
65. Desai S, Tepperman A, Ben Suleiman A, Malkhassian G, Chvartszaid D, Lai JY, et al. Pulpal Deterioration Following Restorative Procedures: A Case - Control Study. *J Endod*. 2025;51(9):1177-1186.
66. Sato T, Matsuyama Y, Fujiwara T, Tagami J. Pulp survival after composite resin restoration of caries lesions in adults. *J Oral Sci*. 2020;63(1):27-30.
67. Chidchuangchai W, Vongsavan N, Matthews B. Sensory transduction mechanisms responsible for pain caused by cold stimulation of dentine in man. *Arch Oral Biol*. 2007;52(2):154-160.
68. Camps J, Pashley D. In vivo sensitivity of human root dentin to air blast and scratching. *J Periodontol*. 2003;74(11):1589-1594.
69. Camps J, Salomon JP, Meerbeek BV, Tay F, Pashley D. Dentin deformation after scratching with clinically-relevant forces. *Arch Oral Biol*. 2003;48(7):527-534.
70. Hajizadeh H, Nemati-Karimooy A, Majidinia S, Moeintaghavi A, Ghavamnasiri M. Comparing the effect of a desensitizing material and a self-etch adhesive on dentin sensitivity after periodontal surgery: a randomized clinical trial. *Restor Dent Endod*. 2017;42(3):168-175.
71. Manz AS, Attin T, Sener B, Sahrman P. Dentin tubule obturation of a bioglass-based dentin desensitizer under repeated exposure to lactic acid and brushing. *BMC Oral Health*. 2019;19(1):274.
72. Ozen T, Orhan K, Avsever H, Tunca YM, Ulker AE, Akyol M. Dentin hypersensitivity: a randomized clinical comparison of three different agents in a short-term treatment period. *Oper Dent*. 2009;34(4):392-398.
73. González-López S, Vilchez Díaz MA, de Haro-Gasquet F, Ceballos L, de Haro-Muñoz C. Cuspal flexure of teeth with composite restorations subjected to occlusal loading. *J Adhes Dent*. 2007;9(1):11-15.

How to cite this article:

Banomyong D. Postoperative Tooth Sensitivity in Direct Resin Composite Restorations: Etiology, Diagnosis, and Management. *J Endod Restor Dent*. 2026; 4(1):15-21. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.18585763

AI Declaration

AI-assisted editing: Grammarly 1.2

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

CRedit Author Statement

D. B. : Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing

Data Availability Statement

No new data were created or analyzed.

Ethics Approval

Not applicable.

Funding

No external funding.

Case Series

Clinical Applications of the Newly Generated MAP VPT System in Different Vital Pulp Therapies: A Case Series

 Sila Nur Usta ^a

^a University of Health Sciences, Gulhane Faculty of Dentistry, Department of Endodontics, Ankara, Türkiye

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 23.11.2025
Completion of First Review: 16.12.2025
Accepted: 04.01.2026
Published: 01.03.2026

KEYWORDS

Endodontics
Pulp capping
Pulpotomy
Vital pulp treatment

CORRESPONDENCE

Sila Nur Usta
University of Health Sciences, Gulhane Faculty
of Dentistry, Department of Endodontics,
Ankara, Türkiye
E-mail: silandeniz29@gmail.com

CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

The MAP VPT system enables accurate and controlled delivery and placement of hydraulic cements, minimizes procedural errors, and enhances efficiency. Its design supports consistent outcomes across different vital pulp treatment, offering clinicians a practical, predictable, and user-friendly approach.

ABSTRACT

This report presents the clinical usability and practicability of the newly-generated MAP VPT system across different vital pulp treatments (VPTs). Three healthy patients with pulpal diagnoses of reversible pulpitis and irreversible pulpitis were treated with direct pulp capping, partial pulpotomy, and total pulpotomy. Following the achievement of hemostasis, mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA) was delivered via the MAP VPT. Patients were recalled at 1 week, 1, 3, 6, and 8 months. In all cases, the system enabled precise and homogeneous placement of the material, reducing procedural time and minimizing contamination risk. Clinical and radiographic follow-ups confirmed asymptomatic, functional teeth with preserved pulp vitality. The present case series highlights the practical advantages of the MAP VPT system in facilitating accurate, controlled, and contamination-free placement of MTA during different VPTs. Further clinical studies with larger sample sizes and long-term follow-up are recommended to comprehensively assess the system's impact on treatment success and material performance.

1. Introduction

Modern endodontic practice has progressively shifted toward the adoption of vital pulp treatments (VPTs), which are founded on biologically oriented and minimally invasive principles.¹ As outlined in the collaborative consensus report by the American Association of Endodontists (AAE) and the European Society of Endodontology (ESE) on diagnostic terminology, even in the case of severe pulpitis, VPTs can be applied.² Therefore, the implementation of a case-specific VPT using scientifically validated biomaterials and clinically appropriate techniques is of paramount importance to preserve pulp vitality and maintain long-term tooth function.

VPTs encompass various treatment modalities, including indirect pulp capping, direct pulp capping, and pulpotomy procedures, depending on the severity and stage of the pulpal pathology.³ During these treatments, one of the key factors is the biocompatible material applied to the pulp tissue.⁴ In this sense, the introduction of mineral trioxide aggregate (MTA) as a biocompatible material into the literature has notably enhanced treatment outcomes by overcoming the drawbacks associated with the use of calcium hydroxide (CH).⁵ Although clinical studies have reported a high success rate of MTA in VPTs,^{6, 7} some clinical properties related to the handling, setting, and discoloration have prompted the development of novel hydraulic cements (HCs) exhibiting diverse chemical compositions and biological characteristics.⁵

Another critical aspect of successful VPTs is the accurate delivery and placement of HC into the pulp chamber. Conventional material delivery during VPTs is commonly performed using spatulas and hand instruments. While these methods are readily available, they

are often technique-sensitive and may be associated with inconsistent material transfer, limited control over placement, increased risk of contamination, and material loss—particularly in deep pulpotomy cavities and molar teeth. These limitations have prompted the development of dedicated carrier systems aimed at improving delivery accuracy and clinical efficiency.⁸⁻¹⁰ Among these, the Micro-Apical Placement (MAP) system has become widely adopted due to its efficiency in delivering HCs into narrow or difficult-to-access areas. However, the conventional MAP system was originally designed for apical and confined operative fields and may be insufficient for VPTs, where wider coronal cavities and the placement of larger volumes of material are required. In such clinical scenarios, limitations related to tip diameter, material flow capacity, and delivery efficiency may compromise homogeneous placement and increase the risk of material loss or prolonged operative time. This represents a specific clinical gap in VPT procedures, where precise, contamination-free, and volumetrically adequate delivery of HCs onto exposed pulp tissue is critical for treatment success. To address this limitation, a modified version of the system—designated as the MAP VPT—has been introduced. This adaptation features a tip with an enlarged internal diameter, specifically engineered to facilitate the controlled placement of the greater HC volumes required for VPT applications. According to the manufacturer, the improved ergonomics and structural robustness of this system enable uniform material delivery with minimal waste, thereby enhancing procedural accuracy and clinical outcomes.¹¹

Although the MAP VPT system was developed towards the end of 2024, its clinical effectiveness has not been demonstrated to date. In this context, the present case series aimed to present the clinical usability and practicability of the MAP VPT system across different VPTs (direct pulp capping, partial pulpotomy, total pulpotomy).

2. Case Presentation

This report of 3 cases was written to comply with the Consensus-based Clinical Case Reporting Guideline (CARE) (Supplementary Material Checklist). All patients were informed about VPTs, including their objectives, potential risks, benefits, and alternatives. Informed consents were obtained, ensuring that they fully understood and agreed to the proposed treatment plan. All procedures were completed in a single appointment by the same endodontist with seven years of experience in the field. For all cases, clinical success was determined by the absence of spontaneous pain, sensitivity to percussion or palpation, swelling, or sinus tract formation, together with a normal, non-lingering response to pulp sensibility testing. Radiographic success was defined as the absence of periapical radiolucency, internal or external root resorption, or other pathological changes (periapical index (PAI)) on periapical radiographs obtained at recall visits.

2.1. Case 1 (Direct pulp capping)

Fig. 1 shows the clinical steps. A 26-year-old healthy female patient presented to the Department of Endodontics with a chief complaint of thermal sensitivity in tooth 37. The patient reported that the discomfort was transient and subsided upon removal of the stimulus. The tooth responded positively to both cold and electric pulp testing (EPT), indicating a vital pulp response, and no sensitivity to percussion or palpation was observed. Periodontal probing depth was <3mm. Periapical radiographic evaluation demonstrated a large restoration with recurrent caries, without periapical radiolucency. Based on these findings, the tooth was diagnosed with reversible pulpitis.

After administration of local anesthesia (2% lidocaine with 1:100,000 epinephrine), rubber dam isolation was achieved, and the operative field was disinfected with 3% hydrogen peroxide

Fig. 1. (A) Pulp exposure, (B) Hemostasis, w/ 3% NaOCl, (C) Confirmation of hemostasis and clean surface, (D) Placement of MTA using MAP VPT, (E) Gently condensation, (F) Confirmation of adequate placement, (G) Preoperative radiograph, (H) 8-month follow-up radiography

Fig. 2. (A) Pulp exposure and bleeding, (B) Hemostasis, w/ 3% NaOCl, (C) Confirmation of hemostasis and clean surface, (D) Placement of MTA using MAP VPT, (E) Gently condensation, (F) Confirmation of adequate placement, (G) Preoperative radiograph, (H) 6-month follow-up radiography

(H₂O₂) for 30 seconds, followed by 2.5% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) for the same duration, and neutralized using 5% sodium thiosulfate. The existing restoration and carious dentin were carefully removed under a dental operating microscope (DOM, LABOMED; Labo America, Inc., Fremont, CA, US) using a sterile round carbide bur in a high-speed handpiece under continuous water cooling. During caries excavation, a pulp exposure was detected. Hemorrhage control was achieved within five minutes by gently applying 3% NaOCl with a sterile cotton pellet. Once hemostasis and a clean surface were confirmed, a thin layer of mineral trioxide aggregate (PD MTA, Produits Dentaires, Vevey, Switzerland) was carefully placed over the exposure site using the MAP VPT (Produits Dentaires, Vevey, Switzerland) system. The material was slightly condensed and covered with a moistened micro applicator for initial setting. Over the MTA, a glass liner (WP Dental, Germany) was placed as a base. Afterwards, Clearfil S3 Bond Universal was applied to the surface using a microbrush and actively rubbed for 10 s. A gentle air stream was then applied for 5 s to evaporate the solvent and form a uniform thin film. The adhesive was light-cured for 10 s using a Cordless LED 1 SEC Curing Light with an irradiance of 1500 mW/cm². Subsequently, the restoration was done with composite (G-aenial Posterior; GC Corporation, Tokyo, Japan), and polished. The patient was recalled at 1 week and at 1, 3, 6, and 8 months. At all follow-up visits, the tooth remained asymptomatic and functional, exhibiting normal responses to pulp sensibility testing and no sensitivity to percussion or palpation. Periapical radiographic evaluation demonstrated the absence of periradicular pathology, root resorption, or other pathological changes (PAI 1), thereby meeting the predefined clinical and radiographic success criteria for cases.

2.2. Case 2 (Partial pulpotomy)

Fig. 2 shows the clinical steps. A 14-year-old female patient without systemic disease was referred to the Department of Endodontics with a complaint of spontaneous and lingering pain in tooth 47. The patient reported sensitivity to thermal stimuli, which persisted after removal of the stimulus. Clinical examination

Fig. 3. (A) Pulp exposure and bleeding, (B) Hemostasis, w/ 3% NaOCl, (C) Confirmation of hemostasis and clean surface, (D) Placement of MTA using MAP VPT, (E) Gently condensation, (F) Confirmation of adequate placement, (G) Preoperative radiograph, (H) 6-month follow-up radiography

revealed a large distal carious lesion, and the tooth exhibited a prolonged positive response to cold and EPT, while percussion and palpation were negative. Periodontal probing depth was <3mm. Radiographic examination showed deep caries approaching the pulp chamber without any signs of periapical pathology. Based on these findings, the tooth was diagnosed with symptomatic irreversible pulpitis.

After obtaining informed consent, preoperative preparations were conducted as described in Case 1. During caries excavation, the distal pulp horn was exposed, accompanied by profuse bleeding. The exposed area and surrounding inflamed coronal pulp tissue in the distal pulp horn were carefully removed using a sterile sharp excavator. Hemostasis was achieved within five to six minutes by gently applying 3% NaOCl with a sterile cotton pellet. Once hemostasis and a clean surface were confirmed, freshly mixed PD MTA was carefully placed over the exposure site using the MAP VPT system, gently condensed, and covered with a moistened micro applicator for initial setting. The permanent restoration was performed as described previously. Follow-up examinations were conducted at 1 week and at 1, 3, and 6 months. Throughout the recall period, the treated tooth remained symptom-free, demonstrated a positive and normal response to pulp sensibility testing, and showed no tenderness to percussion or palpation. Radiographic assessment at each visit revealed normal periapical conditions, with no signs of pathological alterations (PAI 1), confirming the success of treatment.

2.3. Case 3 (Total pulpotomy)

Fig. 3 shows the clinical steps. A 42-year-old healthy female patient presented to the Department of Endodontics with a chief complaint of severe, lingering pain in tooth 47. The pain was exacerbated by exposure to hot and cold stimuli and persisted after the stimulus was removed. Clinical examination revealed an existing occlusal amalgam restoration with recurrent caries. The tooth responded positively to cold and EPT with a prolonged response, while percussion and palpation were negative. Radiographic evaluation demonstrated secondary caries without a periradicular pathology. Based on clinical and radiographic findings, a diagnosis of symptomatic irreversible pulpitis was established.

After obtaining informed consent, preoperative preparations were conducted as described in Case 1. During caries removal, the

pulp chamber was unroofed, and thus, total pulpotomy was performed. Profuse bleeding was controlled by applying 3% NaOCl with a sterile cotton pellet for approximately 8–9 minutes. Once the bleeding had stopped, freshly mixed PD MTA was placed into the pulp chamber floor using the MAP VPT system, gently condensed, and covered with a moistened micro applicator for initial setting. Subsequently, the permanent restoration was performed as described previously. Follow-up evaluations were performed at 1 week and at 1, 3, and 6 months. During all recall visits, the treated tooth showed no clinical symptoms, maintained functional integrity, and exhibited physiologic responses to pulp sensibility testing. Radiographic examination demonstrated stable periapical conditions without evidence of pathological findings (PAI 1), highlighting the success of treatment.

3. Discussion

VPT, as a conservative treatment approach, allows for the preservation of vitality and function of the dental pulp. Especially, the high success rate of VPTs,^{12, 13} combined with ease of application and cost-effectiveness, has led to their widespread adoption as an alternative to root canal treatments. During VPTs, the precise and contamination-free carrying and placement of HC is essential for achieving a hermetic seal and promoting pulp healing. Thus, this case series aimed to demonstrate the clinical usability and practicality of the newly generated MAP VPT system in performing different VPT modalities.

In all three cases, the MAP VPT system demonstrated practical advantages with direct clinical implications. The system enabled single-step delivery of HC directly from the mixing stage to the pulp exposure site, thereby eliminating intermediate transfer steps that are commonly required when using spatulas or micropluggers. This streamlined workflow reduced handling complexity, shortened procedural time, and minimized the risk of material loss or contamination. Additionally, the improved ergonomics and controlled extrusion facilitated consistent material adaptation, particularly in posterior teeth and wider coronal cavities, supporting more predictable and efficient execution of VPTs.

In direct pulp capping procedures, the primary goal is to maintain the health and vitality of the pulp tissue following a small mechanical or carious exposure.¹⁴ Thus, adequately placing HCs directly over the exposed pulp surface is crucial for providing a tight seal and stimulating dentin bridge formation. However, the placement of this material can be technically challenging, especially in confined or deep operative fields. In this present case, MTA was directly placed over a small exposure using MAP VPT. The use of the MAP VPT system enabled precise delivery of the material, minimizing excess material that might interfere with subsequent restorative bonding procedures.¹⁵ Moreover, this application reduced the additional pressure required for adequate condensation of the MTA, which may have contributed to improved surface hardness and, consequently, enhanced compressive strength of the material.¹⁶

In partial pulpotomy procedures, the challenge lies in partially removing inflamed coronal pulp tissue while preserving the vitality of the remaining healthy radicular pulp.¹⁷ During this process, achieving hemostasis and placing the HC over a wider exposure area can be technically demanding, particularly in posterior teeth. In this case report, a relatively larger volume of MTA needed to be placed over a broader exposure area during partial pulpotomy, which can be considered as technically challenging—especially in posterior teeth and distal regions where access and visibility were limited. The MAP VPT system effectively addressed these

challenges by enabling the precise and uniform delivery of MTA directly onto the exposed pulp surface without the need for additional transfer steps. This single and controlled application not only reduced the risk of contamination and material loss but also shortened the operative time while maintaining clinical reliability.

Compared with partial pulpotomy procedures, total pulpotomy requires the placement of a greater volume of HC to achieve complete and hermetic coverage of the entire pulpal floor. The increased cavity dimensions inherently complicate the controlled delivery and adaptation of the material, making precise placement a critical determinant of success.¹⁸ In the present case, the MAP VPT system facilitated the efficient and accurate delivery of an adequate volume of MTA in a single-controlled application. Owing to its specially engineered tip with an enlarged internal diameter, the system allowed for smooth and uniform placement of the material while minimizing procedural time and material waste. This refined delivery approach ensured consistent adaptation of the MTA to the pulpal floor, promoting a dense and stable coronal seal—an essential prerequisite for the long-term clinical success and biological integrity of total pulpotomy procedures.

Despite the encouraging clinical and radiographic findings, the limitations of the present study should be carefully considered. In the scope of the study design, the relatively short follow-up periods (ranging from 6 to 8 months) restrict the ability to draw definitive conclusions regarding the long-term prognosis of the treated teeth. Although the primary objective of this case series was not to evaluate long-term treatment success, but rather to provide an initial clinical insight into MAP VPT's practical usability, handling characteristics, and potential procedural advantages in routine clinical practice, such supportive factors may contribute to overall treatment outcome. Therefore, the present report should be considered exploratory or pilot in nature, and its findings should be interpreted with caution. On the side of the MAP VPT system itself, the relatively high cost of the system may limit its accessibility in general dental settings, especially in universities or clinics with restricted budgets. Moreover, it may require operators to develop new handling skills, particularly regarding angulation, pressure control, and material flow management during treatments. Therefore, there is a need for previous training until adequate familiarity and proficiency are achieved. While the MAP VPT system enhances the precision and uniformity of hydraulic cement placement, the ultimate success of vital pulp treatments remains dependent on other critical parameters, such as accurate case selection, effective hemostasis, maintenance of asepsis, and a well-sealed final restoration. Thus, the system should be considered an adjunct tool that supports optimal material delivery rather than a substitute for sound clinical judgment and biologically based treatment principles.

4. Conclusion

The MAP VPT system could serve as a supportive adjunct for the controlled delivery of HCs during different VPTs. While it can enhance handling convenience and procedural efficiency, treatment success remains dependent on appropriate case selection, effective hemostasis, asepsis, and an adequate coronal seal. Studies with larger patient cohorts and extended follow-up periods are warranted to further validate these findings and to compare the system's efficiency and outcomes with conventional material placement techniques.

References

- Duncan HF. Present status and future directions-Vital pulp treatment and pulp preservation strategies. *Int Endod J.* 2022; 55 Suppl 3(Suppl 3):497-511.
- Updating Diagnostic Terminology in Endodontics. A Collaborative Proposal by the AAE and ESE. Available at: <https://www.aae.org/specialty/diagnostic-terminology-stakeholder-input/>. Accessed 01.10.2025.
- Kahler B, Taha NA, Lu J, Saoud TM. Vital pulp therapy for permanent teeth with diagnosis of irreversible pulpitis: biological basis and outcome. *Aust Dent J.* 2023; 68 Suppl 1(S110-s122).
- Bjørndal L, Simon S, Tomson PL, Duncan HF. Management of deep caries and the exposed pulp. *Int Endod J.* 2019; 52(7):949-973.
- Komora P, Vámos O, Gede N, et al. Comparison of bioactive material failure rates in vital pulp treatment of permanent matured teeth - a systematic review and network meta-analysis. *Sci Rep.* 2024; 14(1):18421.
- Ramani A, Sangwan P, Tewari S, Duhan J, Mittal S, Kumar V. Comparative evaluation of complete and partial pulpotomy in mature permanent teeth with symptomatic irreversible pulpitis: A randomized clinical trial. *Int Endod J.* 2022; 55(5):430-440.
- Dimitraki D, Papageorgiou SN, Kotsanos N. Direct pulp capping versus pulpotomy with MTA for carious primary molars: a randomised clinical trial. *Eur Arch Paediatr Dent.* 2019; 20(5):431-440.
- Giovarruscio M, Uccioli U, Malentacca A, Koller G, Foschi F, Mannocci F. A technique for placement of apical MTA plugs using modified Thermafil carriers for the filling of canals with wide apices. *Int Endod J.* 2013; 46(1):88-97.
- Aminoshariae A, Hartwell GR, Moon PC. Placement of mineral trioxide aggregate using two different techniques. *J Endod.* 2003; 29(10):679-682.
- Farhad A, Sadari AH, Saatchi M, Khademi A, Soltani P. Mineral trioxide aggregate obturation quality with two obturation techniques in severe curved root canals - a micro-CT study. *BMC Oral Health.* 2024; 24(1):968.
- MAP VPT (Produits Dentaires, Vevey, Switzerland). Available at: <https://pd-dental.com/products/map-vpt/>. Accessed 03.10.2025.
- Asgary S, Eghbal MJ, Fazlyab M, Baghban AA, Ghodduzi J. Five-year results of vital pulp therapy in permanent molars with irreversible pulpitis: a non-inferiority multicenter randomized clinical trial. *Clin Oral Investig.* 2015; 19(2):335-341.
- Asgary S, Eghbal MJ, Shahravan A, Saberi E, Baghban AA, Parhizkar A. Outcomes of root canal therapy or full pulpotomy using two endodontic biomaterials in mature permanent teeth: a randomized controlled trial. *Clin Oral Investig.* 2022; 26(3):3287-3297.
- Islam R, Islam MRR, Tanaka T, Alam MK, Ahmed HMA, Sano H. Direct pulp capping procedures - Evidence and practice. *Jpn Dent Sci Rev.* 2023; 59(48-61).
- Cervino G, Fiorillo L, Spagnuolo G, et al. Interface Between MTA and Dental Bonding Agents: Scanning Electron Microscope Evaluation. *J Int Soc Prev Community Dent.* 2017; 7(1):64-68.
- Rao A, Rao A, Shenoy R. Mineral trioxide aggregate--a review. *J Clin Pediatr Dent.* 2009; 34(1):1-7.
- Wazurkar S, Patel A, Chandak M, et al. Preserving Vitality: A Case Report of Partial Pulpotomy in Dental Practice. *Cureus.* 2024; 16(6):e61720.
- Duncan HF, El-Karim I, Dummer PMH, Whitworth J, Nagendrababu V. Factors that influence the outcome of pulpotomy in permanent teeth. *Int Endod J.* 2023; 56 Suppl 2(62-81).

Acknowledgments

The author would like to thank Mr. Alexandre Mulhauser from Produits Dentaires for kindly providing the prototype of the MAP VPT system before its official launch.

AI Declaration

No generative AI used for writing/analysis/figures.

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

CRedit Author Statement

S. N.U. : Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Visualization

Data Availability Statement

All data are included in the article and its supplements.

Ethics Approval

Not applicable.

Funding

No external funding.

How to cite this article:

Usta SN. Clinical Applications of the Newly Generated MAP VPT System in Different Vital Pulp Therapies: A Case Series. *J Endod Restor Dent.* 2026; 4(1):22-26.
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.18586004

Case Report

Separated Instrument Retrieval from the Maxillary Canine using only Ultrasonic Energy and Non-Vital Bleaching with Hydrogen Peroxide: A Case Report

Abdumelik Buğrahan Kızıl^a, Edanur Maraş^a, Muhammed Enes Naralan^b

^a Recep Tayyip Erdoğan University, Faculty of Dentistry, Department of Endodontics, Rize, Türkiye

^b Recep Tayyip Erdoğan University, Faculty of Dentistry, Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Radiology, Rize, Türkiye

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 08.11.2025
Completion of First Review: 16.12.2025
Accepted: 31.12.2025
Published: 01.03.2026

KEYWORDS

Cone-beam computed tomography
Root canal therapy
Separated instrument
Tooth bleaching

CORRESPONDENCE

Abdumelik Buğrahan Kızıl
Recep Tayyip Erdoğan University, Faculty of
Dentistry, Department of Endodontics, Rize,
Türkiye
E-mail: kizilabdumelik@gmail.com

CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE

This case demonstrates that the exclusive use of ultrasonic energy allows for safe and conservative retrieval of a separated instrument, while subsequent non-vital bleaching with hydrogen peroxide effectively restores aesthetics in discoloured teeth.

ABSTRACT

A fractured file within the root canal system can hinder the root canal's mechanical and chemical cleaning, adversely affecting the treatment prognosis. Ineffective cleaning of the root canal system and the corrosion of the fractured instrument within the canal can lead to tooth discoloration. This case report presents the successful removal of an obliquely positioned fractured instrument in a partially obliterated and discoloured maxillary right canine tooth using only ultrasonic energy, followed by non-vital bleaching with hydrogen peroxide. It emphasizes the efficacy of integrating ultrasonic tools, a dental operating microscope, and cone-beam computed tomography in treating such challenging cases. The removal of the fractured instrument using ultrasonic tips can be defined as a safe and conservative technique. Non-vital bleaching can provide quick, cost-effective, and aesthetically pleasing results in discoloured teeth with pulp canal obliteration, which can be challenging for clinicians.

1. Introduction

Instrument fracture is a highly distressing complication with an incidence rate of 0.25-6% during root canal treatment.¹ A fractured instrument creates significant challenges, including the possibility of canal corrosion and obstruction of cleaning and shaping procedures. Therefore, bypassing or removing the fractured instrument is necessary to access the apex.² Orthograde removal of the fractured instrument is often time-consuming and difficult, with a success rate of 55-79%.³ Depending on the technique used, potential outcomes during preparation include perforation, extrusion, additional instrument fracture, and excessive loss of radicular dentin. Therefore, risk assessment is crucial in managing this complication.⁴

For instance, an engaged instrument adheres to the canal wall, exhibiting greater resistance to removal due to increased torsional connection.¹ Hence, preoperative identification of factors such as the position, angle, and length of the fractured file is a prerequisite for successful treatment.⁴ Removal attempts require the use of a non-invasive or minimally invasive technique with an appropriate methodological approach under good visualization.⁵

Minimally invasive approaches are paramount in these scenarios. Ultrasonic technology has revolutionized the management of intracanal obstructions, offering a superior alternative to traditional mechanical methods. By utilizing high-frequency vibrations, ultrasonic tips can selectively remove dentin surrounding the fractured segment without imposing excessive stress on the root structure. When combined with visual magnification, such as a dental operating microscope, ultrasonic energy facilitates precise trenching around the fragment, loosening it through vibration and acoustic streaming, thereby

enhancing the predictability of retrieval.¹

Teeth are significant elements for first impressions and psychosocial well-being. Even a single tooth colour discrepancy can be easily perceived by individuals, disrupting the harmony of a smile. Correctly identifying the etiology of discoloration is crucial for the clinician to apply adequate treatment.^{6,7} Known etiological factors for discoloration in endodontically treated teeth include materials containing silver, Mineral Trioxide Aggregate (MTA), temporary restorations, and remnants of pulp tissue after treatment.

It is important to emphasize that inadequately performed root canal treatments are a predominant etiology of intrinsic tooth discoloration. When the root canal system is not thoroughly debrided and obturated—often a consequence of procedural errors like instrument fracture—necrotic pulp tissue remnants and blood breakdown products penetrate the dentinal tubules. Over time, the degradation of these organic substances releases chromogenic compounds that significantly alter the optical properties of the tooth structure.^{8,9}

Additionally, caries, pulp necrosis, trauma, and canal calcifications are common causes of internal discoloration.⁸ In endodontically treated teeth with significant discoloration, bleaching is a less invasive and economical treatment option compared to full crowns, veneers, and composite restorations.⁹

This case report aims to present the successful removal of an obliquely positioned fractured file in the coronal-middle third region of a discoloured and partially obliterated maxillary right canine tooth using ultrasonic energy and non-vital bleaching with hydrogen peroxide.

2. Case Presentation

A 54-year-old male patient with no pain or symptoms presented to the Department of Endodontics, complaining about the unesthetic appearance of his maxillary anterior tooth. The patient had no systemic conditions and was not on any medications that could cause tooth discoloration. A detailed anamnesis revealed that the affected tooth had undergone treatment 20 years ago, but the patient could not recall the exact procedure.

Clinical examination revealed a mismatched composite restoration and intense gray discoloration on the maxillary right canine (#13) (Fig. 1a). The tooth was not sensitive to percussion. Electric pulp testing (Parkell Digitest II, NY, USA) and cold testing (Pulp Spray, CerKamed, Stalowa Wola, Poland) indicated that the tooth was non-vital. Periapical radiography (Xmind Satelec-Acteon X-ray source, Mérignac, France; 70 kV, 10 mA, and 100 ms) showed no pathology in the periapical region. A radiopaque foreign body was observed apical to the coronal third of the root canal space. The canal space could not be fully visualized coronal to the radiopacity (Fig. 1b).

For a more detailed radiological examination, the patient was referred for cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT). CBCT images were acquired using a Planmeca ProMax 3D Classic (Planmeca Promax 3D; Planmeca Oy; Helsinki, Finland) with the following parameters: 90 kV, 10 mA, 15.02 seconds, 8x8 cm field of view (FOV), and 75 µm voxel size. Although smaller fields of view (e.g., 5x5 cm) are typically preferred for single-tooth endodontic procedures to minimize radiation dose, an 8x8 cm FOV was selected. This larger volume provided a more comprehensive view of the surrounding anatomical structures, including the entire maxillary arch, the adjacent teeth, and the periapical region, to fully rule out pathology, assess the full extent of the root, and confirm the canal anatomy in a complex case involving instrument fracture and partial calcification. The acquisition process was performed according to the manufacturer's recommended protocol. The measurements were performed using Planmeca Romexis 4.6.2.R software (Planmeca Romexis, Helsinki, Finland). Patient gave informed consent for the use of their X-ray examination in scientific research.

CBCT evaluation showed a hyperdense foreign object approximately 2 mm long extending buccally and obliquely at the

Fig. 1. Preoperative clinical and radiographic findings. a. Preoperative intraoral picture with discolored tooth; b. Initial periapical radiograph revealing a radiopaque foreign body in the root canal space of the maxillary right canine; c. Cone beam computed tomography view (0.1 mm thick, 0.2 mm spaced cross sectional sections) revealing hyperdense foreign object 2 mm long extending buccally and obliquely in the canal and partial obliteration

Fig. 2. Endodontic procedures. a. Verification of separated instrument retrieved and determination of working length; b. Glass ionomer cement barrier; c. Photograph showing 48 hours follow up showing complete bleaching of intrinsic stains; d. Periapical radiograph showing post endodontic restoration

junction of the coronal and middle thirds of the canal (Figure 1c). Partial obliteration of the root canal coronal to the fractured instrument was also confirmed. There was no pathology in the periradicular region. The patient gave informed about the treatment options and possible outcomes related to the management of the fractured instrument and post-endodontic whitening. Non-surgical root canal treatment followed by non-vital bleaching was decided upon.

After obtaining written informed consent, local infiltration anaesthesia was administered to tooth #13 using 2% articaine with 1:120,000 epinephrine (Ultraver D-S Forte 80 mg + 0.03638 mg/2 ml, HAVER FARMA, İstanbul, Türkiye). Under rubber dam isolation, the old restoration was removed using an air turbine handpiece and diamond fissure bur with copious irrigation. A cotton pellet left under the restoration was removed. The carious tissue at the distal step was completely removed using slow-speed round carbide burs.

Under a dental operating microscope (DOM; Zeiss Extaro 300, Oberkochen, Baden-Württemberg, Germany) at 16X magnification, cement residues in the coronal part of the canal were removed using an ED3D ultrasonic tip (Woodpecker Co., Guilin, Guangxi, China). After the fractured instrument became visible at 16X magnification, it was loosened using an ultrasonic device (DTE S6, Guilin Woodpecker Co.) and an ED87 ultrasonic tip (DTE, Guilin Woodpecker Co.; mode: E, setting: 2) specially designed for instrument removal. To ensure safety and reproducibility, the device was operated in 'Endo' mode (Mode E). The power intensity was carefully modulated, set to 'Setting 2', which corresponds to approximately 20% of the maximum power output. This lower power setting was selected to minimize the risk of heat generation and microcracks in the root dentin.¹⁰ The ultrasonic activation was applied in short, intermittent bursts (5–10 seconds) to facilitate controlled dentin removal while maintaining constant visibility and cooling.^{1,5}

The dentin around the fractured instrument's coronal portion was removed 360 degrees. The instrument was loosened but did

Fig. 3. Postoperative follow-up at 6 and 12 months.

(a) Clinical photograph and periapical radiograph obtained at the 6-month follow-up; (b) Clinical photograph and periapical radiograph obtained at the 12-month follow-up.

not dance because it was stuck to the buccal wall. Therefore, preparation was performed between the instrument and the buccal wall using the same tip. Frequent pauses were taken for cooling, and 2.5% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) irrigation was performed. Passive ultrasonic activation (PUI; TD2; DTE, Guilin Woodpecker Co.; mode: E, setting: 6) was conducted during irrigation to better clean dentin debris. The amount of loosening of the instrument was increased using silicone-based oil and ultrasonic tips. Once dancing was observed, 17% ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) was filled up to the cavosurface. The ED87 ultrasonic tip was activated in a coronal-apical direction, and within approximately 10 seconds, half of the file popped out of the canal. The remaining buccal piece of the file was removed using the same technique with the ultrasonic tip placed between the instrument and the buccal wall.

Periapical radiography confirmed the removal of the fractured instrument. Vital pulp tissue was observed apical to the fractured instrument. After the pulp was extirpated, the working length was determined using an electronic apex locator (Root ZX, J. Morita Co., Tokyo, Japan) and periapical radiography (Fig. 2a). The canal preparation was performed by Scope RS (Gtech, Yozgat, Türkiye) files up to K7 Gold (30/0.04). During instrumentation, the canal was irrigated with 2.5% sodium hypochlorite. The final irrigation was performed using PUI (TD2; DTE, Guilin Woodpecker Co.; mode: E, setting: 6) with 2.5% sodium hypochlorite and 17% EDTA. The canal was dried with paper points and filled using the lateral compaction technique with gutta-percha and resin-based root canal sealer (ADSEAL; Meta Biomed Co., Cheongju, Korea).

After removing gutta-percha 2 mm apically from the cemento-enamel junction, the cavity was washed and dried. Glass ionomer cement (Ruby liner, Madrid, Spain) was applied over the gutta-percha as a barrier material to minimize bleaching agent leakage. For managing the gray crown, 35% hydrogen peroxide (Opalescence™ Endo, Ultradent, Utah, USA) was injected into the chamber, and a cotton pellet was placed. The access cavity was temporarily sealed with glass ionomer cement (Nova Glass F, Imicryl, Konya, Türkiye) (Fig. 2b).

The patient was recalled for evaluation 48 hours later. After a single bleaching session, the desired results were achieved, and the patient was satisfied (Fig. 2c). Hydrogen peroxide was removed from the pulp chamber using copious saline irrigation. Calcium hydroxide paste was then placed in the pulp chamber for seven days. The tooth was later restored with resin composite (FGM Llis, Santa Catarina, Brazil) (Fig. 2d). At the 6- and 12-month follow-up

appointments, the tooth remained asymptomatic and no pathology was observed on periapical radiography. The patient was also satisfied with the aesthetic outcome (Fig. 3).

This case report has been written according to Preferred Reporting Items for Case reports in Endodontics (PRICE) 2020 guidelines (Supplemental File 1).¹⁰

3. Discussion

Instrument fracture during endodontic treatment is a highly distressing complication that can adversely affect treatment procedures and prognosis. Depending on the moment of the accident and the level of the root canal where the instrument fractures, proper shaping and filling of the canal may be hindered.¹¹ Improperly filled canals and the corrosive products caused by the instrument can lead to tooth discoloration.^{2, 8} This case report describes the treatment of a maxillary canine that had become partially calcified and discoloured following inadequate endodontic treatment and instrument fracture.

Instrument fractures during endodontic treatment obstruct apical access, preventing the complete realization of root canal therapy.¹¹ In this case, in addition to the failure to fill the apical portion due to the instrument fracture, the coronal part of the canal was also left unfilled. The vital pulp in the apical portion suggests that the instrument likely broke during the early stages of the procedure, possibly during canal exploration. According to Berman and Hargreaves, management strategies for separated instruments range from non-surgical orthograde retrieval to surgical intervention. Since the fragment was located in the coronal third of the root canal, a non-surgical orthograde approach was selected as the most conservative and least invasive treatment modality.¹²

Approaches to fractured instruments include non-surgical orthograde and surgical methods. In this case, the fractured instrument was close to the coronal section of the root canal, leading to the selection of a non-surgical orthograde approach as a less invasive option.² The orthograde approach involves bypassing, removing, or obturating at the level of the fractured instrument.⁴ According to Machtou and Reit, the best course of action in the presence of a fractured instrument is to remove it.¹³ The decision to prioritize the ultrasonic technique over other retrieval methods, such as mechanical extractors or bypassing, was driven by the need for hard tissue preservation. Although bypassing the instrument may be considered a viable alternative, this approach does not eliminate the intracanal obstruction and may compromise effective cleaning and disinfection of the apical third.

For instrument removal, several mechanical retrieval systems, such as the Masserann kit and the Endo Extractor, have been introduced. However, these techniques are associated with notable limitations, including excessive radicular dentin removal, increased risk of perforation and canal deviation, restricted applicability in narrow or curved canals, and possible apical extrusion of the fragment.² In particular, mechanical extraction systems often require substantial dentin sacrifice to engage the fractured instrument, which may significantly weaken the root structure and increase the risk of vertical root fracture.^{2,14} Given these drawbacks, the use of non-invasive or minimally invasive techniques is advocated for the management of fractured instruments.²

The ultrasonic technique is a minimally invasive method that uses ultrasonic vibrations to loosen and then extrude the fractured instrument from the canal. With advancements in this technique, the removal of fractured instruments has become more predictable and less invasive.^{2,5} Therefore, in this report, ultrasonic energy was utilized to remove the fractured instrument. Ultrasonic

tips were used with a DOM to ensure a clear view and to minimize damage to the radicular dentin.²

For better visibility and to reduce the likelihood of procedural errors, it is recommended that the root canal preparation be performed in a dry environment when using a DOM during attempts to remove fractured instruments.^{12,15,16} Therefore, root canal preparation for instrument removal should be done in a dry environment.¹² Accordingly, in this report, the preparation with ultrasonic tips was conducted dry. To prevent temperature increase and secondary fracture, the tip was used at 20% of the maximum power setting with back-and-forth movements.^{1,17,18} It has been reported that to attempt to remove the broken tool, the tool should be seen dancing ("not flexing" or "dancing"), not flexing.¹² In this case, after a 360-degree opening of the coronal part of the instrument, only flexing was observed. Therefore, to achieve the dancing movement and proceed with removal attempts, apical preparation was made between the fractured instrument and the buccal wall.

Terauchi et al. reported that most fractured instruments smaller than 4.6 mm could be removed within 10 seconds using only the ultrasonic method.^{1,19} This method involves filling the canal with EDTA up to the cavosurface (not just the root canal) and using ultrasound to take advantage of cavitation and acoustic streaming. The ultrasonic tip is operated with short up-and-down strokes on the inner curve until the instrument is removed. A higher power setting of 10%-20% more can be used during the preparation stage as the ultrasonic tips are more resistant to breakage in wet conditions than in dry conditions.^{1,20} Similarly, in this case, after observing the dancing movement, EDTA was filled up to the cavosurface, and a straight ED87 ultrasonic tip, specially designed for instrument removal, was placed between the instrument and the buccal wall, and activated with short up-and-down strokes.

Despite efforts to prevent secondary fracture during the procedure, the instrument came out in two pieces, possibly due to its oblique positioning in the canal. Additionally, in this case, before attempting removal with EDTA, silicone-based oil was used to loosen the file from the canal wall and was then removed with paper points.¹²

Terauchi et al.,¹ stated that the treatment protocol for removing a fractured instrument should be determined based on CBCT findings. The initial periapical radiograph identified a radiopaque foreign body but provided limited information on its three-dimensional location and the full anatomy of the canal. The subsequent CBCT examination was therefore instrumental in clarifying the treatment strategy. By accurately localizing the fragment at the buccal aspect and revealing the extent of canal obliteration, the CBCT images guided the precise angle and depth of ultrasonic troughing, thereby reducing the risk of iatrogenic errors such as perforation.^{1,21} In line with this, in this case, CBCT was used before the procedure to confirm the presence of the fractured instrument, determine its location, and understand the canal anatomy.¹ However, high atomic number materials cause various artifacts. Although not entirely preventable, the degree of artifact is directly proportional to the FOV area, meaning fewer artifacts occur in low FOV scans than in high FOV scans.²¹ In this case report, a small FOV was selected to minimize artifacts, and the presence of foreign material inside the tooth was observed. Although smaller fields of view (e.g., 5x5 cm) are typically preferred for single-tooth endodontic procedures to minimize radiation dose, an 8x8 cm FOV was selected. This larger volume provided a more comprehensive view of the surrounding anatomical structures, including the entire maxillary arch, the adjacent teeth, and the periapical region, to fully rule out pathology, assess the full extent of the root, and confirm the canal anatomy in a complex case involving instrument fracture and partial calcification.^{21,22}

Despite 20 years passing since the initial treatment, no periapical pathology developed in this case. This could be due to the intact apical pulp circulation resisting bacterial invasions.²² However,

CBCT sections showed partial obliteration of the canal coronal to the fractured instrument. The mechanisms underlying canal obliterations are still unclear. It is believed that the reduction in canal lumen after trauma results from excessive dentin apposition due to pulp healing rather than pulp pathology.²³ In this report, damage to the neurovascular bundle and the maintenance of the remaining pulp vitality may have caused excessive dentin apposition, leading to canal narrowing.^{22,24} Terauchi et al. noted that any overhangs coronal to the fractured instrument that could obstruct its removal should be eliminated using rotary instruments or ultrasonic tips.¹ In this case, considering the presence of calcification, the coronal part of the fractured instrument was modified using an ultrasonic tip.

The gray discoloration in the crown of the present case could be attributed to various factors. Partial pulp necrosis, remnants of canal paste or cement, or corrosion of the fractured instrument inside the canal could have darkened the tooth.^{2,8,23} Yellow discoloration is a common finding (8%-79%) in teeth with canal obliteration. In contrast, gray discoloration is rarely seen (1%).²³ Oginni et al. reported graying in 34 out of 276 teeth with obliterated canals.²⁵ The gray discoloration observed in this case may also have resulted from partial obliteration of the canal.^{23,24} Non-vital bleaching is a more minimally invasive procedure than traditional treatments such as laminate veneers and full crowns for discoloured non-vital teeth.²⁶ The literature supports the placement of a cervical barrier and the use of 35% hydrogen peroxide as a bleaching agent without heat activation for longer-lasting and faster effects in discoloured teeth. During and after bleaching, a 2 mm layer of glass ionomer cement prevents the diffusion of the hydrogen peroxide solution.⁶ In this case, glass ionomer was placed as a 2 mm thick base, and 35% hydrogen peroxide was used as the bleaching agent. Heat was avoided during bleaching to prevent the possibility of initiating cervical resorption.²⁷ Additionally, as the pH drop caused by hydrogen peroxide plays a role in external root resorption, temporary dressing with calcium hydroxide was used for buffering purposes.¹²

Initially, the tooth in this case did not respond to vitality tests and was considered necrotic, leading to the commencement of treatment. Following the removal of the fractured instrument, the presence of healthy pulp observed under DOM and the ensuing bleeding led to the suggestion of vital pulp therapy using calcium silicate cements for the patient. However, a pulpectomy was performed based on the patient's decision. Calcification in the coronal part and the vital pulp starting at the middle third level of the canal may have caused the initial devital response.^{23,28} During primary endodontic treatment, the inflamed or necrotic pulp tissue might have been removed, preserving the vitality of the remaining pulp. This aligns with current biologically based endodontic treatments.²⁹ Therefore, the potential for vital pulp to be present apical to inadequately filled root canals should not be overlooked in cases similar to the one presented here.

4. Conclusion

Due to the lack of a standard treatment protocol for instrument removal, a comprehensive assessment of the situation is necessary before the procedure. The use of ultrasonic tips with DOM has been identified as a predictable and conservative technique for removing fractured instruments. Non-vital bleaching provides rapid, cost-effective, and aesthetically pleasing results for discoloured teeth with pulp canal obliteration. Additionally, the possibility that the pulp tissue apical to the fractured instrument may remain vital should not be disregarded.

References

1. Terauchi Y, Ali WT, Abielhassan MM. Present status and future directions: Removal of fractured instruments. *Int Endod J.* 2022;55:685–709.

2. Hindlekar A, Kaur G, Kashikar R, Kotadia P. Retrieval of separated intracanal endodontic instruments: A series of four case reports. *Cureus*. 2023;15(3):e35694.
3. Umre U, Sedani S, Nikhade PP, Mishra A, Bansod A. The good old Masserann technique for the retrieval of a separated instrument: An endodontic challenge. *Cureus*. 2023;15(9).
4. Kadoo S, Patni PM, Jain P, Agrawal N, Raghuvanshi S, Pandey SH. An unusual case of maxillary first molar with seven canals and the successful surgical recovery of a separated instrument. *J Conserv Dent Endod*. 2024;27(2):21
5. Kaul R, Gupta R, Chhabra S, Koul R. Dental operating microscope-guided retrieval of broken instrument from a deciduous molar using ultrasonics. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent*. 2022;15(Suppl 1):114–118.
6. Javed MQ, Saleh S, Ulfat H. Conservative esthetic management of post-orthodontic treatment discolored tooth with calcified canal: A case report. *Pan Afr Med J*. 2020;37:254.
7. Kılıç Y, Karataşlıoğlu E, Tatar B, Şahin O, Tulgar M. Aesthetic rehabilitation of complicated crown fractures in a single visit: Case series. *Turk Endod J*. 2021;6(3):92–96.
8. Kahler B. Present status and future directions: Managing discoloured teeth. *Int Endod J*. 2022;55(Suppl 4):922–950.
9. Barakah R, Alwakeel R. Non-vital endo-treated tooth bleaching with sodium perborate. *Curr Health Sci J*. 2019;45(3):329–332.
10. Nagendrababu V, Chong BS, McCabe P, Shah PK, Priya E, Jayaraman J, et al. PRICE 2020 guidelines for reporting case reports in endodontics: A consensus-based development. *Int Endod J*. 2020;53:619–626. doi:10.1111/iej.13285.
11. Amza O, Dimitriu B, Suciul I, Bartok R, Chirila M. Etiology and prevention of an endodontic iatrogenic event: Instrument fracture. *J Med Life*. 2020;13(3):378–381.
12. Berman LH, Hargreaves KM. Cohen's pathways of the pulp. 11th ed. St. Louis: Elsevier Health Sciences; 2020.
13. Reit C, Bergenholtz G, Bindsvlev PH. *Textbook of endodontology*. Oxford: Wiley-Blackwell; 2010.
14. McGuigan M, Louca C, Duncan HF. Clinical decision-making after endodontic instrument fracture. *Br Dent J*. 2013;214(8):395–400.
15. Souter NJ, Messer HH. Complications associated with fractured file removal using an ultrasonic technique. *J Endod*. 2005;31(6):450–452.
16. Suter B, Lussi A, Sequeira P. Probability of removing fractured instruments from root canals. *Int Endod J*. 2005;38(2):112–123.
17. Cujé J, Bargholz C, Hülsmann M. The outcome of retained instrument removal in a specialist practice. *Int Endod J*. 2010;43(7):545–554.
18. Tzanetakis GN, Kontakiotis EG, Maurikou DV, Marzelou MP. Prevalence and management of instrument fracture in the postgraduate endodontic program at the Dental School of Athens: A five-year retrospective clinical study. *J Endod*. 2008;34(6):675–678.
19. Terauchi Y, Sexton C, Bakland LK, Bogen G. Factors affecting the removal time of separated instruments. *J Endod*. 2021;47(8):1245–1252.
20. Malki M, Verhaagen B, Jiang LM, et al. Irrigant flow beyond the insertion depth of an ultrasonically oscillating file in straight and curved root canals: Visualization and cleaning efficacy. *J Endod*. 2012;38(5):657–661.
21. Codari M, de Faria Vasconcelos K, Ferreira Pinheiro Nicolielo L, Haiter Neto F, Jacobs R. Quantitative evaluation of metal artifacts using different CBCT devices, high-density materials and field of views. *Clin Oral Implants Res*. 2017;28(12):1509–1514.
22. Robertson A, Andreasen FM, Andreasen JO, Noren JG. Long-term prognosis of crown-fractured permanent incisors: The effect of stage of root development and associated luxation injury. *Int J Paediatr Dent*. 2000;10(3):191–199.
23. Bastos JV, Côrtes MIS. Pulp canal obliteration after traumatic injuries in permanent teeth: Scientific fact or fiction? *Braz Oral Res*. 2018;32:e159.
24. Andreasen JO, Andreasen FM. *Textbook and color atlas of traumatic injuries to the teeth*. Copenhagen: Munksgaard; 1994.
25. Oginni AO, Adekoya-Sofowora CA, Kolawole KA. Evaluation of radiographs, clinical signs and symptoms associated with pulp canal obliteration: An aid to treatment decision. *Dent Traumatol*. 2009;25
26. Badole GP, Warhadpande MM, Bahadure RN, Badole SG. Aesthetic rehabilitation of discoloured nonvital anterior tooth with carbamide peroxide bleaching: Case series. *J Clin Diagn Res*. 2013;7(12):3073–3076.
27. Félix-Matos L, Hernández LM, Abreu N. Dental bleaching techniques: Hydrogen and carbamide peroxides and light sources for activation—An update. *Open Dent J*. 2014;8:264–268.
28. McCabe PS, Dummer PMH. Pulp canal obliteration: An endodontic diagnosis and treatment challenge. *Int Endod J*. 2012;45(2):177–197.
29. Schmalz G, Widbiller M, Galler KM. Clinical perspectives of pulp regeneration. *J Endod*. 2020;46(9 Suppl):S161–S174.

AI Declaration

No generative AI used for writing/analysis/figures.

Conflict of Interest

All authors declare no conflicts of interest.

CRediT Author Statement

A.B.K. : Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing-original draft, Visualization

E.M. : Methodology, Writing-original draft, Writing-original draft, Writing-review & editing, Supervision

M.E.N. : Investigation, Writing-review & editing.

Data Availability Statement

No new data were created or analyzed.

Ethics Approval

Not applicable.

Funding

No external funding.

How to cite this article:

Kızıl AB, Maraş E, Naralan ME. Separated Instrument Retrieval from the Maxillary Canine using only Ultrasonic Energy and Non-Vital Bleaching with Hydrogen Peroxide: A Case Report. *J Endod Restor Dent*. 2026; 4(1):27-31. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.18586263